

2nd E.T. Hanrahan Memorial Lecture

GEOTECHNICAL PROPERTIES OF IRISH COMPRESSIBLE SOILS

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River Shannon Bridge / Athlone Bypass (Photo Gabriel Corcoran Westmeath Co. Co.)

SYNOPSIS

The objectives of this paper are to provide an update on work done and the development of knowledge on Irish compressible soils since Eamon Hanrahan's 1979 book on the topic. Eamon subdivided these soils into three categories namely alluvial, estuarine and lake deposits and he termed them "troublesome soils". A brief background geology will initially be presented. The complexity of the deposits both on a macro and micro scale will be highlighted. Sites which have been well studied will be summarised and the engineering solutions used to construct on these sites will be reviewed. Although work on these sites presents a significant engineering achievement, some important lessons were learned. The remainder of paper deals with how these lessons might be addressed in the future. For example how can modern ground investigation techniques be used to best characterise these complex deposits and what are the best techniques for examining important detailed aspects of 1D consolidation behaviour such as the identification of the preconsolidation stress, the sometimes rapid rate of consolidation and creep and also how to characterise the undrained shear strength of the soils. The work will be benchmarked against experience of the behaviour of Scandinavian soft soils.

INTRODUCTION

Eamon Hanrahan is perhaps best known for his work on peat. Certainly his two Géotechnique papers on the subject of peat are his best known works internationally. However he wrote two books on other important Irish sub-soils namely glacial till deposits (Hanrahan, 1977) and on Irish compressible soils – excluding peat (Hanrahan, 1979). Eric Farrell provided an excellent update on the properties of Irish glacial and interglacial soils in his 2016 Hanrahan Lecture (Farrell, 2016).

The objectives of this paper are to provide an update on work done and the development of knowledge on Irish compressible soils since Eamon's 1979 book. The paper will deal with the background geology of the materials, the complexity of the soils, summarise sites where good data exists on the soils and also give an overview of the construction techniques used. Some details of several of these sites will be given. Existing and more recently developed site investigation techniques, such as piezocone testing (CPTU) and the use of geophysics (particularly shear wave velocity), will be reviewed. Sample disturbance effects will be assessed. Finally the determination of 1D compression parameters and undrained shear strength will be discussed in detail. Peat will not be considered and only a limited discussion on calcareous marl is included.

Since the publication of Eamon's book in 1979 there have been several other important contributions to the topic especially:

- Geotechnical Society of Ireland (GSI) / Engineers Ireland (EI) Seminar on "Road Embankments on Soft Ground in Ireland" held at EI on 14/3/96 and edited by E. Farrell, B. Lehane, M. Long & T. Paul.
- GSI / EI Conference on "Soft Ground Engineering" held at Portlaoise on 15 and 16 February 2007 and edited by M. Long, P. Jennings and P. Rutty
- GSI / EI Conference on "Geotechnics on Irish Roads, 2000 – 20110: A Decade of Achievement" held in Portlaoise on 11 October 2012 and edited by F. Buggy, E. Farrell, P. Quigley and M. Robinson.

All of these publications contain valuable data and case histories some of which will be referred to later.

BACKGROUND GEOLOGY

Hanrahan (1979) sub-divided Irish compressible soils into three categories namely alluvial, estuarine and lake deposits. He termed these soils "troublesome" and suggested that all these materials have been deposited since the end of the last glacial period about 10,000 years ago. The focus of this paper will be on these three soil types. Of course other soft soils exist in Ireland such as soils which were formed by slumping from weathered hills and drumlins but these will not be considered. Peat will also not be dealt with. Findings for Irish soft soils will be supported by data on Norwegian soft clays – as these soils form the basis of the author's experience.

Alluvial deposits

It is beyond the scope of this paper to describe in detail the geological origin and formation of alluvial deposits. According to Waltham (2009) alluvial soils are river deposited sediments which are sorted and bedded but can

contain any grain size from clay to boulders. These soils are laterally and vertically variable with a wide range of engineering properties. This definition certainly holds true for Irish alluvial deposits and from a geotechnical engineering perspective these soils are highly complex and variable. They can contain random layers and lenses of clay, silt, sand, gravel and even large boulders. Organic material can also be frequently found.

Estuarine deposits

Since the last glacial era sea level has risen by 100 m or so. The retreating ice sheet produced large quantities of melt water and sediment. Rivers transported newly formed soils to the coastline. These deposits are largely granular in nature comprising complex deposits of gravel, sand and silt. In many Irish coastal areas, though there is no doubt some fluvial contribution to the deposits, soft soils mainly of estuarine origin are often encountered. These were deposited in relatively shallow water in less dynamic conditions. Occasionally, during periods when the land was dry, deposits of organic soils including peat formed in distinct lenses within the coarser mineral soils. From a geotechnical point of view the result is a complex sequence of soils, which requires thorough investigation.

Lake bed soils

Deglaciation

As the characteristics of these soils will be dealt with in some detail later, their geological history is considered more thoroughly as follows. Much of this discussion in the following section has been extracted from Delaney (1995), Mitchell and Delaney (1997) and Van der Meer and Warren (1997). The last glaciation of the area, often termed the Late Midlandian glaciation, and which occurred some 20,000 to 12,000 years before the present (B.P.) dominates the geological history of the Central Lowlands of Ireland. The ice sheet was composed of a number of ice domes. These had begun as individual ice caps and they subsequently coalesced to form an ice sheet covering almost the whole of Ireland. Finally they re-emerged as individual ice bodies during deglaciation, see Figure 1. As can be seen from this figure the ice supported an extensive body of standing water, known as a proglacial lake. The darker shading represents the extent of the lake at various positions of the ice front. Figure 1(a) shows the early stages of deglaciation, in (b) the ice domes have separated, in (c) the ice domes have retreated to their centers of dispersion and (d) shows the substantial flooding caused by ice blocking the two main catchments.

The wide distribution of the glaciolacustrine deposits in the area confirm that the lake was an extensive body of water which covered the Midlands, see Smith (1994) and Mitchell and Delaney (1997). Initially the lake was supported almost entirely by ice margins but later became increasingly supported by land. Data from the elevation of delta surfaces suggest that the proglacial lake surface was at approximately 92 mOD and that therefore its depth was approximately 50 m in the vicinity of Lough Ree and about 30 m at Clara and Raheenmore bogs, some 35 km to the southeast.

Figure 1. Schematic postulated depiction of deglaciation (Van der Meer and Warren, 1997)

Inorganic laminated clays / brown laminated clays

According to Rodgers and Fahy (1995) as the ice retreated a maze of pool and shallow lakes developed in the Irish Midlands. Inorganic clays were deposited in these water bodies from the melt waters and from erosion of the land probably some 20,000 to 16,500 years B.P. The lacustrine deposits were slowly laid down in a seasonally rhythmic pattern of varved clays, silts and sands. Towards the base of the lake laminae thickness are of the order of 100 μ m to 2 mm and occur in regularly banded rhythmites which indicate seasonal variation in sediment input into the lake. Darker coloured clay laminae are thinner and were deposited in very still water conditions over relatively long periods when little or no meltwater was entering the lake. Lighter coloured thicker silt laminae were deposited when meltwater input was low. The rate of deposition of the material was of the order of 0.6 to 1 mm per year, which is on the lower limit of the deposition rates for other lacustrine deposits (Hight et al., 1987). At Athlone, for example, the varves are almost horizontal and are typically 1 mm to 2 mm thick. These deposits are often referred to as the brown laminated clays, see Figure 2.

Figure 2. Athlone brown laminated clay from about 9.1 m depth. Sample is 100 mm in diameter.

Readvance of the glacier

There is evidence for a subsequent readvance of the glacier, see Delaney (1995) or McCabe (1987). Delaney (1995) suggests that the readvance occurred over the brown clay sediments either by (a) flotation in a standing body of water or (b) sliding over the low shear strength deposits by the formation of a thin shearing zone. This may have caused some overconsolidation of the brown laminated clay.

Organic clays / grey organic clay

As the climate became warmer, so the depositional environment changed from glacio - lacustrine to floodplain, with a rapid increase in organic content. These grey organic clays are not always present indicating a fairly complex sequence of erosion surfaces during post - glacial times.

Calcareous marl

Overlying these deposits is a layer of white calcareous soil, known locally as "calc marl" or simply "marl". It is made up almost entirely of calcium carbonate (CaCO_3) and is formed as a result of CaCO_3 coming out of solution, due to either physico - chemical or biological factors. It is precipitated on top of the lake deposits from water arising from adjacent lime rich strata flowing upwards through the lake bed clays under artesian conditions. If water saturated with CaCO_3 , in equilibrium with CO_2 levels greater than normal atmospheric, comes into contact with the atmosphere CO_2 diffuses out causing the water to be saturated with CaCO_3 resulting in deposition. Calcareous soils can also be brought about by biological processes. Certain plants can uptake and utilise bicarbonate ions for photosynthesis resulting in direct precipitation of calcium carbonate on their leaves and stems. The calc marl is often cellular in nature and may enclose pieces of plants or animal remains.

There has been much debate in the literature as to the relative importance of physico-chemical and biological factors in the formation of calc marl (Hammond et al., 1987). Materials similar to the Irish calc marls are found in many other places around the world, see for example Murphy and Wilkinson (1980), Ford and Pedley (1996) or Diefendorf et al. (2008). Following the precipitation of the calc marl vegetation begins to grow in and around the pools and lakes ultimately leading to the formation of raised bogs. The calc marl is clearly distinguishable from the underlying lake bed clays and the overlying peat due to its creamy white colour, see Figure 3.

Figure 3. Peat overlying calcareous marl and lake bed clays (photo courtesy of Andy Trafford)

Work on the properties of Irish calc marl has been undertaken by various authors such as Dr. Cathy Delaney at Manchester Metropolitan University, see for example Delaney (2009). Some discussion on the engineering properties of the material are given by Long and Rodgers (1995). From an engineering point of view the material has significant importance in the Galway area, see Quigley et al. (2016).

COMPLEXITY OF IRISH COMPRESSIBLE SOILS
Macro-scale issues

Bearing in mind the complex geological history of the sediments it is very important to bear in mind that Irish compressible soils can be highly complex in nature both on a macro-scale and micro-scale level. These issues will be discussed as follows and Irish soils will be contrasted to soft soils from Norway. Many of the correlations between various engineering parameters, which have been published in the literature, concern very uniform soils, such as the Norwegian clays, and therefore great care needs to be taken when transferring the lessons learned elsewhere to Irish conditions.

Micro-scale issues – evidence from scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

Coy (2002) undertook a detailed study of the microstructure of 12 Irish soils (in addition to pure kaolin clay as a reference soil) using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). His work revealed the large variability and complexity of the soils – particularly the soft deposits. Some examples from his work follow. For example he found that the microstructure of the estuarine silts was particularly complex. An example from the Sligo-Colooney Bypass site is shown on Figure 4.

Figure 4. SEM image of Sligo estuarine silt (Coy, 2009)

The Sligo organic silt was found to be dominated by a seemingly chaotic arrangement of silt particles in a very porous fibrous calcitic matrix. Also abundant within the calcitic matrix were sand grains and large aggregations. Individual clay particles and aggregations were numerous but irregularly scattered. Several unidentified organic structures were found – possibly of fungal origin. Pyrite nodules, the result of post-depositional mineral growth, were also found within the soil. While pores within the fibrous matrix were typically small (<1 µm), larger pores (>5 µm) were sometimes found.

The microfabric of the Athlone brown clay, Figure 5, is consistent on a broad scale, but locally variable, being a

regular combination of dispersed and flocculated arrangements of clay plates with frequent silt grains. There is considerable matrix clay, arranged in random flocculated and honeycomb structures, between the dispersed clay stacks and silt grains. No evidence of organic content or mineral growth was found. The pore spaces within the random flocculated matrix clay were typically found to be relatively small (< 1 µm), however pores within the honeycomb arrangements were larger (>2 µm). Larger pores (4 µm) were found in areas between clay stacks where no matrix clay was present.

Figure 5. SEM image Athlone brown laminated clay (courtesy Yoko Tanaka, PHRII, Japan)

STUDY SITES

Table A (at the rear of the paper) summarises the well characterised soft ground sites in Ireland where data on the sites is available in the public domain. The sites are divided into those underlain by post glacial clays, alluvial clays and silts. Data is available for some 40 sites comprising a large body of valuable data. The location of these study sites is shown on

Figure 6. The post-glacial lake-bed clay sites are mostly grouped around the western midlands, consistent with the previous large pro-glacial lake system (Figure 1).

Figure 6. Location of study sites

There are also some of these sites located at other locations such as Loughmore and Bundoran-Ballyshannon where presumably there were smaller lakes in the past. The alluvial clay sites are mostly located at the mouths of significant rivers such as the Shannon, Suir, Slaney, Avoca and Lee. The silt sites are all located in estuarine areas all around the island.

ENGINEERING SOLUTIONS PREVIOUSLY USED ON SOFT SOIL SITES

A summary of engineering solutions used at the soft soil sites, shown on Figure 6, are summarised on Table A (rear of report). The objective of introducing these data in the paper at this stage is to review the success or otherwise of these schemes, to study the lessons learned and to examine which ground properties and behaviour are best and least understood.

In most cases the engineering problem involved the construction of embankments on the soft soils. In many cases the embankments were of relatively modest height. However the soft ground thickness was often considerable. The overall success of these schemes represents a considerable achievement by Irish engineers.

Note that a list of projects where piled embankments were used to support the imposed loads is included on Table A for completeness. A study of the behaviour of piled embankments on soft soils is beyond the scope of this paper.

A summary of the construction techniques used at each site is shown on Figure 7. The sites are divided into those on post-glacial clays, alluvial clays and silts. Note at three of the sites two distinct construction techniques were used and these sites have been considered to be two sites for the sake of this analysis.

The sum of experience for all sites is shown on Figure 8. Some points to note are as follows:

- It is very likely that the number of excavate and replace cases is underestimated due to lack of reporting. Frequently excavate and replacement is carried out in conjunction with other techniques when the soft deposits are less than say 5 m thick.
- Otherwise surcharging with vertical drains dominates the techniques used.
- Surcharging was used without vertical drains on four out of eleven silt sites and on two out of ten alluvial clay sites.
- No treatment was used on three silt sites.
- There are eight recorded cases of piled embankments which have not been included here.
- There has also been a limited use of LECA lightweight fill on the M7/M8 and the Bunratty Bypass (www.leca.co.uk).

Figure 8. Summary of construction techniques used at all sites

Figure 7. Summary of construction techniques used for (a) post-glacial clay sites, (b) alluvial clay sites and (c) silt sites

Lessons learned from construction experience

A summary of some of the lessons learned, as reported in the various accounts of construction on the sites summarised on Table A is given on Figure 9. Some significant points from this compilation are:

- In general the predictions of primary compression have been good ($\pm 20-30\%$).
- However the rate at which primary compression occurs is often underestimated. This could be due to lack of identification of silt / sand layers and underestimation of the coefficient of consolidation (c_v or c_h).
- There are a few cases where slow primary compression has been blamed on possible smearing of vertical drains, but this is not easy to prove conclusively.
- The importance of correctly identifying the preconsolidation pressure (p_c') has been stressed several times.
- Creep settlements are often significant and have sometimes been under-estimated. Clearly creep settlements are difficult to estimate accurately.
- There are a number of reported significant embankment failures and some minor failures. Three of the significant failures were on post-glacial lake clay sites and two on alluvial clays. The reasons for these failures are complex and often due to a combination of factors.

All of these issues will be addressed in the sections on the various engineering parameters that follows.

Figure 9. Summary of lessons learned from construction experience

DETAILS OF SOME SELECTED SITES

Athlone Bypass (Post-glacial lake bed soils) – Site 1

The route of the Athlone Bypass passes to the north of the town and is 8.9 km long. Major bridges carry the Bypass over the River Shannon and the Roscommon railway. The 1.25 km length of the Bypass, approximately between the bridges, which traverses the flood plain of the River Shannon was known to flood regularly and to be underlain by very soft soils. Between the bridges and to their east and west sides the Bypass construction required embankments up to 8.6m above the level of the flood plain, see Figure 10.

Athlone town is situated on an esker ridge that is aligned east - west. The town buildings and major structures are virtually all located on this ridge of well graded sands and gravels. The ridge is thought to have been breached during the meltwater events of the Pleistocene period, creating the precursor to the River Shannon flood plain. Prior to that breach a glacial lake had formed to the north of the esker and lacustrine deposits (known as the brown laminated clays) were laid down in the manner described above. Later the depositional environment changed from glacio - lacustrine to floodplain, with a rapid increase in organic content. Overlying these deposits is a layer of calc marl. A thin layer of peat completes the sequence.

The deposits are complex in the Athlone area and a cross section through the site is shown on Figure 11.

Figure 10. Athlone Bypass - site layout and location

Here the focus is on Profile D where the best quality samples are available as will be discussed later. A summary of the ground conditions at this location is given on Figure 12. A high degree of natural material variability is exhibited, particularly for the grey organic clay. Water content values decrease from about 100% at the top of the grey organic clay to some 60% at its base and then further decrease to about 30% at the base of the brown laminated clay. There is a parallel increase in bulk density from about 1.4 Mg/m³ to 2 Mg/m³. The grey organic clay is of medium to high plasticity whereas the brown laminated clay is of medium plasticity. Both materials are slightly overconsolidated, due to a fluctuating water table and possible glacier re-advance, and are very soft with the brown clay having vane shear strengths of only 4 to 5 kPa.

Figure 11. Cross section through Athlone Bypass

Figure 13. Clonmore Link Road and Joe Dolan Bridge, Mullingar (Photograph courtesy Michael Kelly Westmeath Co. Co.)

Figure 12. Athlone Bypass - Profile D - Index properties

Clonmore Link Road, Mullingar (Post-glacial lake bed soils) – Site 12

The Clonmore Link Road is located just south of Mullingar, Co. Westmeath and connects the Clonmore area to N52 (Tullamore Road) and thus also to the N4 (Mullingar Bypass). The link road crosses a valley running north-east from Lough Ennell. This valley has been infilled with a considerable depth of very soft ground and to the knowledge of the author this site is perhaps the deepest area of soft ground in Ireland where the geotechnical properties of the soils have been well investigated. The geology of the site is very similar to that of the Athlone Bypass, see above and it is located towards the centre of the proglacial lake, see Figure 1.

A view of the site is shown on Figure 13. Geotechnical work on the site was undertaken initially by AGL Ltd. and subsequently by Roughan and O'Donovan and Fehily Timoney Gifford Ltd. Ground investigations were carried out by Westmeath Co. Co., IGSL and Fugro. The data presented here was supplied to the author by Westmeath Co. Co. Various options were considered for the road construction so as to take the vertical alignment above the flood protection level and over Lacy's Canal and the River Brosna, see Figure 13 and Figure 14. Finally a bridge was constructed for much of the length of the Link Road over the soft ground area. This bridge is now known as the Joe Dolan Bridge.

Figure 14. Geological cross section through Clonmore Link Road

A geological cross section along the Link Road is shown on Figure 14. A considerable thickness of peat and calc marl (up to 11.6 m) overlies a soft clay / silt to a maximum depth of over 28 m. The soft ground is underlain by glacial sand and gravel and then limestone bedrock.

Three site investigations, which included soil sampling and testing, were carried out on the site (by Westmeath Co. Co. and AGL in 2004, by IGSL in February 2008 and again by IGSL in August 2008). Some geotechnical index properties for the soils are shown on Figure 15. The index properties reveal three distinct strata as had been identified in the borehole logs. There are no significant differences in the results between the three investigations. There is however considerable scatter in the data as is often encountered in Irish soft soils.

The data for the soft clay / silt is again shown on Figure 16. Here the data for the peat and calc marl have been omitted and the x-axis scales changed for emphasis. It can be seen that material in the upper zone of the soft clay / silt has higher water content. This suggests that as at Athlone the material has relatively high organic content and was deposited in a warmer period. Also the consistency in the parameters of the lower zone of the material and the relatively low water content suggest that it might be lightly overconsolidated (perhaps due to glacial re-advance as at Athlone).

Figure 15. Clonmore Road - index properties of soils

Figure 16. Clonmore Road - index properties of soft clay / silt

Nonetheless despite the complexity of the deposits, their thickness and the presence of three distinct strata render the site ideal for further study.

Fort Henry Embankment – Shannon hydroelectric scheme (Alluvial deposits) – Site 17

The Shannon embankments were constructed in the period 1926 to 1928 as part of the River Shannon hydro-electric scheme. They comprise those forming the 11.5 km headrace canal and two embankments namely Fort Henry and Ardcloney which form the storage reservoir just south of Lough Derg, see Figure 17.

The embankments were built on the alluvial deposits of the River Shannon at a time when little was known about soil mechanics. Various stability problems have been encountered, particularly over the early years of the life of the scheme. These included small slides, slumps, cracks and seepages (Massarsch et al., 1987). However in recent years there have been very few problems, with the scheme operating efficiently.

This is largely due to the great care and diligence taken by the ESB who are responsible for the scheme.

Fort Henry embankment is some 2.7 km long and up to 8.5 m high and was built between 1927 and 1928 using boulder clay fill from a nearby borrow pit. Compaction of the fill was achieved by slewing the railway track supplying the fill as construction proceeded. Two significant failures have occurred, one on the downstream side at C/S 100 in 1948 (Harty, 1953) one on the upstream face at C/S 57 in 1979, see Casey et al. (2002) and Long et al. (2002). The embankment is heavily instrumented with piezometers, standpipes, tensiometers, seepage monitoring points, levelling points and movement monitoring stations. The embankment (along with all of the Shannon embankments) is physically inspected daily. Continuous monitoring data for some 90 years is available making these structures arguably the best monitored in Ireland.

The ground conditions beneath the embankments are highly variable and complicated, consistent with experience of alluvial deposits elsewhere. An example from near C/S57, where the 1948 failure took place is shown on Figure 18 and Figure 19.

Figure 17. View of Parteen Weir with Fort Henry embankment on upstream right hand side, Ardcloney embankment to the left and the beginning of the Headrace embankment on the lower left hand side (Photo courtesy Senan Mc Evoy – ESB)

At this particular location a thin layer of soft / firm clay / silt overlies loose to medium dense silty sand, which in turn overlies glacial deposits. However conditions change significantly over short distances. The case of Fort Henry supports the idea that in order to characterise Irish alluvial soil sites a significant amount of site investigation is necessary.

Figure 18. Fort Henry Embankment C/S 57 - basic parameters

Figure 19. Fort Henry Embankment C/S 57 - particle size distribution tests

Foynes Harbour Access Road (Silts) – Site 30

The Foynes Harbour access road site is a good example of a well characterised Irish silt site. Basic properties of the soils are shown on Figure 20. Although this might appear quiet subtle at first glance, the site is underlain by two distinct layers: an upper sandy silt, which transitions at 5.5 to 6.5 m into a lower clayey silt. Water content is more variable in the upper sandy silt and ranges between 15% and 40%. Below 6.5 m the water content is relatively uniform at about 37%. Similarly there is a significant scatter of bulk density values above 5.5 m ranging from 1.8 to 2.15 Mg/m³. Bulk density is reasonably uniform from 5.5 to 12.0 m with an average value of 1.9 Mg/m³. The organic content of the soil is very low with an average value of roughly 2%.

The transition from a sandy silt to a clayey silt can also be seen clearly on Figure 20c. Above 5.5 m the sand content is about 10% and this drops close to zero in the lower layer. There is also a gradual increase in clay content and a reduction in silt content with depth. A line corresponding to 15% clay content is also shown on Figure 20c. According to Norwegian practice if a material has a clay content of more than 15% then it behaves in a clay like manner (NGF, 2011). It would seem that the Foynes data is consistent with this finding.

Particle size distribution curves, shown on Figure 21a, also confirm the increasing fines content in the material with depth. Atterberg limit test results, shown on Figure 21b clearly separate out the two layers with the upper layer showing “silt” behaviour and the lower layer “clay” behaviour.

SITE INVESTIGATION TECHNIQUES FOR SOFT GROUND

Shell and auger drilling

The most common technique used to investigate soft ground in Ireland is by shell and auger drilling (cable percussive boring). The technique had been used for many years and its popularity is mainly due to the low costs involved and the relative ease of getting the drilling rig onto difficult sites. There are significant issues relating to accurate identification of the soil layers encountered, the measurements of depth and to safety issues such as injuries associated with lifting and hand injuries. Here the focus is on the disturbance that is caused to the base of the borehole prior to sampling.

Factors such as swelling, remoulding, base heave, piping and caving, all caused by the drilling technique, will inevitably cause sample disturbance. These problems are summarised by Clayton et al. (1995) and Hight and Burland (1990). Aspects of the problem are similar to base heave in deep excavations in soft clays as researched, for example in the classic paper by Bjerrum and Eide (1956). These authors conclude that base failure is very likely in normally consolidated clays and, that in lightly overconsolidated clays, the strains at the base of the excavation will be so high that the underlying soil will be severely affected.

Figure 20. Foynes Harbour access road - index properties

Figure 21. Foynes Harbour access road (a) particle size distribution curves and (b) A line chart.

Figure 22a shows the results of some numerical analyses (assuming elastic soil with $K_0=1.0$) which investigated the changes in total horizontal ($\Delta\sigma_h$) and vertical stress ($\Delta\sigma_v$) as well as the change in pore water pressure (Δu) below the base of a borehole during drilling (Hooper, 1992). It can be seen that the stress changes are significant and extend well below the base of the borehole. This has significant implications for sampling the material in this disturbed zone.

As pointed out by Ladd and DeGroot (2003) drilling to the sampling depth reduces the total vertical stress, and therefore subjects the clay at the bottom of the hole to undrained shear in triaxial extension (TE). In practice in the US and elsewhere drilling mud is used to prevent failure in TE. If the weight of the drilling mud is too low, the soil at the bottom of the borehole can experience an undrained failure in TE before even being sampled. This is illustrated in Figure 22b.

In Ireland Z_w is often very low. Therefore the borehole needs to remain filled with drilling mud having a weight that falls at least half way between a state of failure (lower three lines) and perfect sampling (upper three lines), i.e. it must weigh about 1.25 times that of water in order to prevent excessive disturbance before sampling.

As drilling mud is generally not used in Ireland and as sometimes boreholes are not kept topped up with water it is strongly possible that the subsequent sampling is being done in material which is at least highly strained and possibly already failed.

Sampling soft ground in Ireland

Piston sampling

For important projects (starting with the investigation for the Athlone Bypass in 1980), thin walled 100 mm diameter fixed piston samples, locally known as ELE 100 mm samples, are usually obtained. Usually a hole is advanced to the required depth using the shell and auger technique. The borehole is supported with temporary casing and kept topped up with water to minimise instability at the base of the hole.

Figure 22. (a) Stress changes below the bottom of a borehole from Hooper (1992) and (b) Effect of drilling mud weight and depth to water table on borehole stability for OCR = 1 clays (Ladd and DeGroot, 2003)

The sampler is then lowered to the sampling depth, with the piston located at the base of the tube to prevent ingress of soil. During sampling the inner rods and piston are fixed in a locked position and the outer rods are pushed down at a constant rate. After the sample is obtained, the inner rods can be removed as the piston is fixed relative to the sample tube. Withdrawal of the sampler and the outer rods can then take place.

In Ireland, the sample tubes normally have a 30° edge cutting angle or have been sharpened to a 5° cutting angle. Clayton et al. (1998), Hight (2001) and others have suggested that samples of improved quality can be obtained by this simple modification. At the Dunkettle, Sligo and Portumna sites, sampling has also been carried out using the Norwegian Geotechnical Institute (NGI) 95 mm diameter sampler (Andresen, 1981).

In order to investigate the effects of borehole drilling Donohue (2005) and Donohue and Long (2010) used the Scandinavian “displacement” approach at the Ballinasloe research site.

(b)

Here the sampler (with the piston fixed in position at the front of the sample tube) is pushed to the desired depth without pre-boring. The sample is then taken in the normal way. Such an approach requires soft ground in order to penetrate the equipment.

In Ireland efforts have also been made to retrieve “undisturbed” samples by means of conventional open drive U100 tubes. In particular in silty soils, two U100 tubes have been screwed together in an attempt to recover sufficient sample for later testing. This approach is called “double U4 sampling”

Dimensions and features of these samplers are summarised on Table 1. The requirements of the Eurocode for Class 1 samples (ENISO, 2006) are also shown on the table. Note that only the ELE tube with the taper edge angle sharpened to 5° strictly complies with the Eurocode requirements. However, as will be demonstrated later, strict adherence to the dimensions given do not necessarily guarantee Class 1 samples, as many other factors come into play when determining the final sample quality.

Table 1. Dimensions and features of samplers

Sampler	Length cm	D_e cm	D_w cm	D_s cm	Area ratio %	Cutting edge angle degrees	Inside clearance %	Drilling technique
ELE 100	100	10.14	10.48	10.14	6.8	30, 10 or 5	0	Mostly pre-auger
NGI 95	100	9.63	10.16	9.66	11	9	0.3	Pre-auger
Double U100	90	10.14	11.44	10.14	27	60 and 15	0	Pre-auger
MOSTAP-65	200	6.5	9.3	6.5	105	15	0	Via CPT
MOSTAP-70	100	7.0	7.0	7.0	6	6	0	Via CPT
Sherbrooke	35		25					
Eurocode Class 1 requirement	45-100	5-12			<15	<5	0.5-1.0	

Notes: D_e = inside diameter of cutting shoe,
 D_w = outside diameter of cutting shoe,
 D_s = inside diameter of sampling tube,

$$\text{Area ratio} = (D_w^2 - D_e^2)/D_e^2,$$

$$\text{Inside clearance} = (D_s - D_e)/D_e.$$

Continuous sampling

In Ireland continuous soil samples of 65 mm in diameter can be obtained using the MOSTAP® 65 sampler. MOSTAP stands for the *Monster Steek Apparaat*, roughly translated as sample stick apparatus. Further details are given by Weltman and Head (1983) and Long (2002). For this technique no borehole is required and it is usually used in conjunction with CPT testing. At the predetermined depth the cone face is pulled inward to allow the MOSTAP apparatus to be pushed to the specified sampling depth. To maintain sample quality, a thin walled (2 mm) sample tube with a stocking can be used for better support of the sample during the sampling process and during transportation to the lab. The liner acts as a guide for a piston during sampling and distributes a stocking uniformly around the sample. The purpose of the stocking is to minimise friction. Up to now the actual sampler used has a cutting edge angle of 15° and an area ratio of about 105%. Thus it would be expected to yield relatively poor soil samples if those were required for say oedometer and triaxial testing. This has been shown to be the case. Nevertheless the continuous samples are excellent for site profiling.

Due to the relatively poor quality of the samples the manufacturers of the MOSTAP sampler A.P. van den Berg have recently developed an improved version of the sampler. The new design known as the MOSTAP 70 replaces the older MOSTAP 65. Its design is based partly on the work done to develop a high quality deep-water offshore sampler as described by Lunne and Long (2006) and Lunne et al. (2008). Samples of diameter 70 mm are obtained (Figure 23). The apex angle is reduced to 40° and the cutting shoe is provided with a 6° degree cutting edge angle. With the new design it is possible to retrieve the sample in portions of 1 m. The use of a core catcher and stocking is optional, depending on soil type and sample conditions .

Figure 23. MOSTAP 70 sampler (a) cone and sampler head and (b) sampler cutting edge

Given the issues with instability at the base of boreholes this is an interesting development and some work to trial the technique in Ireland and to investigate the quality of the resulting samples is well warranted.

Downhole block sampling

It has long been recognised that the highest quality samples can be obtained by block sampling. In Ireland block samples have frequently been taken from cuttings or excavation pits. Heymann and Clayton (1999), for example, give good advice on the best procedures that should be used in these circumstances. However cuttings or excavation pits are often not available – especially at the start of projects. In these cases a downhole block sampler is required.

Figure 24. Sherbrooke block sampling at Athlone

To the authors knowledge there is only one example of the use of a down-hole block sampler in Ireland. The Sherbrooke block sampler was used at the site of the Athlone Bypass (Long, 2006b), see Figure 24. At Athlone samples were extracted from within a 450 mm diameter borehole.

This borehole was advanced using a flat-bottomed auger in order to minimise disturbance effects at the base of the hole. A short length of temporary casing was used to stabilise the top part of the borehole. This allowed the water, which supported the borehole, to be maintained at a level above ground. Full details of the sampler are given by Lefebvre and Poulin (1979). It uses three circumferential cutters combined with water pressure to core out an annulus around a block of soil to be sampled. Once the full length of the annulus is cored, three horizontal spring activated, bottom cutters are released to cut the bottom of the sample and provide basal support for retrieving it. A full sample measures 250 mm diameter by 350 mm tall (Figure 24).

Field vane testing

Previous use of the field vane

Field vane testing has been frequently used in Irish soft soils. Many different types of vane have been used for example the Farnell field vane or the Geonor vane probe. These vanes are rectangular in shape, typically 75 mm diameter by 150 mm long. Testing is carried out during the drilling of conventional shell and auger boreholes with the vane being pushed out approximately 1 m below the base of the borehole (and the casing). The vane is rotated at a rate of about 7° / minute. The borehole is then advanced to the depth of the last vane test before proceeding with the next test. A dummy rod fitted in place of the vane was used to measure the friction on the embedded length of the rods.

Figure 25. (a) Geonor vane borer and (b) vane insertion disturbance effects Loughmore Link Road

The Geonor vane borer was designed to eliminate rod friction, see Figure 25a. The vane is protected by an outer sheath during penetration. The vane is pushed beyond this sheath on reaching the required depth. Various vane sizes have been used, for example 50 mm x 100 mm or 65 mm x 130 mm. Otherwise the test procedure is as for the Farnell field vane as described above.

Hand vane (19 mm x 38 mm) and lab vane (13 mm x 26 mm) tests have also been carried out.

In the authors opinion great care needs to be taken when using the results of the above tests on Irish soft soils. Data from the construction of the Athlone embankments confirms the work of others, for example Aas et al. (1984) or Chandler (1987), in that it was found that the field vane significantly underestimates the operational strength of the clays. This was attributed to a combination of inaccurate assumptions regarding stress distribution around the vane, strength anisotropy and most especially vane insertion disturbance effects. In particular care needs to be taken when interpreting the results of the tests for soils which are likely to be subjected to surcharging, in which the gain in strength of horizontal surfaces of the soil is much more than on the vertical surfaces. It is these latter surfaces which are sheared during vane testing.

An example of the effects of vane insertion disturbance are shown on Figure 25b. The data is from the Loughmore Link Road project, see Figure 6 and Table A. The Geonor vane borer was used in all three cases. The results produced by Contractor No. 1 are very low and well below the line representing $0.25\sigma'_{v0}$ in the brown clay. Contractor 2's and UCD's results seem much more reasonable.

In contrast in silty soils drainage of excess pore water pressures can occur during the testing resulting in values of s_u that are higher than the true in situ value

Recent developments in vane testing

Recent developments of in situ vane testing techniques have mostly made use of improved data gathering and recording systems. Advanced vane testing systems record torque down-hole rather than at the surface and torque and time are recorded continuously, typically at 1 Hz (Peuchen and Mayne, 2007).

These systems are most commonly used offshore (see for example www.fugro.com) but are also used for advanced onshore application (www.envi.se or www.geotech.se).

For example in the “Memovane” produced by the Swedish company ENVI (www.envi.se), measurement takes place immediately above the vane, thus avoiding the influence of friction on the rods, see Figure 26a. An aluminium shoe protects the vane during penetration and cleans the vane after each test. The gearbox is located in the vane unit so the rotation takes place down the hole.

Data is sent acoustically to a laptop at the surface. This makes it possible to use the vane at great depths. The vane can be either 55 mm x 110 mm or 60 mm x 120 mm. Data is recorded as stress versus time rather than a simple peak and residual value, thus giving additional valuable data on the material and allowing the results of the test to be carefully assessed. An example is shown for the Onsøy site on Figure 26b.

Figure 26. (a) ENVI Memovane (b) example result from Onsøy

Cone penetration testing

Checks and corrections

There seems little doubt but that the CPTU is now the most widely used in situ testing device for soft ground throughout the world (Long, 2008). For a full description of the equipment the reader is referred to the textbook by Lunne et al. (1997b) and to the European Standard (ENISO, 2012). In the opinion of the author the test is extremely powerful in soft soils. However, as with any sensitive electronic equipment, it is possible to get unreliable data if the proper procedures are not applied and the correct checks and corrections are not made.

In particular is very important to properly saturate the pore water pressure filters. As will be explained the pore water pressure data is particularly useful and lack of saturation will lead to misleading results. The most important checks and corrections that need to be applied to CPTU results are:

- i. Correction for pore pressure effects using the formula:

$$q_t = q_c + (1 - \alpha)u_2 \quad (1)$$
 where q_t = corrected cone resistance; q_c = measured cone resistance; α = area ratio (typically = 0.8); u_2 = measured pore pressure behind the cone tip
- ii. Correction for inclination
- iii. Transducer drift (shift in zero values)
- iv. Temperature

It is vital that the user of the data checks that correction (i) is done correctly to the European Standard. In particular the user should check the correct α has been used. Ideally α should be determined experimentally in a simple calibration chamber, as the actual α can vary considerably from the theoretical depending on how the seals are fabricated. The influence of item (ii) is usually low, except in deep deposits, but a simple correction can be made according to the European Standard. Frequently issues (iii) and (iv) can have a very significant influence in the results.

These two factors are interrelated as one main reason for the shift in reference values is temperature effects. However other factors such as load cell hysteresis can also alter the zero reference values. It is vital to check the load cell readings immediately on extraction, to assess whether there has been any drift.

Typical results

Some typical CPTU results for soft soils at Clonmore Road and Onsøy are shown on

Figure 27. The Clonmore Road test was carried out by Fugro using a 10t cone and that at Onsøy using an A.P van den Berg cone (Test CPTU009). The results are broadly similar. Over the top 20 m at both sites cone resistance, corrected for pore pressure effects (q_t) is of the order of 0.2 MPa to 0.8 MPa. The Clonmore Road test result clearly shows the presence of a sandy lens between 15.5 m and 17 m. Sleeve friction (f_s) values are very low and are of the order of 5 to 20 kPa. Pore pressure was measured in the u_1 position (on tip face) at Clonmore Road and at the u_2 position (just behind tip) at Onsøy. Values are in the order of 0.2 MPa to 0.6 MPa.

It is important to assess these results in the context of Application Class 1 (for use in soft soils) of the European Standard, which requires that the “minimum allowable accuracy” should be the larger of:

- $q_t = 0.035$ MPa or 5% of measured value
- $f_s = 5$ kPa or 10% of measured value
- $u_2 = 0.01$ MPa or 2% measured value

It can be seen that for both the Clonmore Rd. and Onsøy tests, the measured q_t and u_1/u_2 values are significantly greater than the required accuracy. However the f_s values are often less than the value required by the Standard. Measured sleeve friction will be influenced by (Lunne et al., 1986, Lunne et al., 1997b, Lunne et al., 2018):

- Condition / wearing of steel in sleeve,
- Interface friction between the soil and the sleeve

Figure 27. CPTU results for (a) Clonmore Road and (b) Onsøy

- Pore pressure effects on the ends of the friction sleeve. This effect depends on the actual areas at each end of the sleeve and the difference in pore pressure at the top (u_3) and bottom (u_2). A correction should be made if possible.
- Tolerance and dimensions between the cone and the sleeve
- Load cell design and calibration.

Influence of different equipment / comparative studies

Recent studies and experience show that even if the European Standard is followed the results can still vary significantly according to the equipment used. For example, a series of parallel CPTU's were carried out at Onsøy. Seven different cones from five manufacturers were used in the comparative exercise at the Onsøy NGTS site (Lunne et al., 2018). The main objective of the work was to check the influence of equipment type and to evaluate if cone penetrometers used for commercial and research projects can meet the requirements of Application Class 1 of the European Standard. The results are shown on Figure 28 and it can be seen that:

- the range of q_t and u_2 values is well in excess of the requirement of Application Class 1. However the range of f_s values is of the same order of magnitude.
- The scatter in u_2 values is relatively small (data for Cone 6 which had a slot filter rather than a regular filter slightly higher).
- Compared to u_2 the scatter in q_t values is slightly higher.
- f_s values show relatively large variations

Gauer et al. (2002) summarised a comparable earlier study at Onsøy which gave similar results. Long (2008) reports on a number of similar studies in UK and in the Netherlands which yielded the same result. Good practice following the European Standard will reduce the variation from one test to another. If the pore pressure measurement system is sufficiently well saturated the measured pore pressure is the parameter that shows least variation from one type of CPTU equipment to another.

The q_t values show somewhat more variation from one type of equipment to another as compared with the measured pore pressure. Measured sleeve friction shows most variation from one type of equipment to another and these values should be treated with caution. Lunne et al. (2018) studied some of the reasons for the variation in f_s values but concluded that there are still unanswered questions. From the above it should be expected that derived soil parameters or soil classification based on pore pressure readings should be expected to be more reliable compared to classification based on sleeve friction measurements. This topic will be addressed later. Nonetheless it is recommended that pore pressure readings should be included in all routine investigations.

Advances in techniques used in Ireland

Perhaps the most significant advances made in the technique in Ireland involve the development of equipment that permits access to difficult sites, e.g. those over soft ground. Some examples include the system developed by In Situ Site Investigations Ltd. who have developed a system of detachable rams welded onto an excavator, see Figure 29a and the tracked “bogskipper” rig of Lankelma Ltd., see Figure 29b. These rigs provide both the reaction force and the flexibility needed to access the different locations quickly.

Full flow probes

Although it is generally accepted that the CPTU is the most useful tool for profiling shear strength in soft soils, there are some sources of potential inaccuracy associated with the equipment itself. These include the often very low q_t values in Irish soils, the relatively small bearing area of the cone perhaps not accounting for macro-scale effects and also the “out of balance “ pore water pressure corrections that need to be made (Formula 1).

Development of the T-bar and other similar devices has been driven by attempts to overcome these inaccuracies. Typically the bearing area of the T-bar is 10 times that of the cone, see Figure 30, thus improving the accuracy of

Figure 28. Results of comparative CPTU test program at Onsøy (Lunne et al., 2018)

Figure 29. (a) In Situ Site Investigation Ltd. - system with detachable rams and (b) Lankelma Ltd. “bogskipper” tracked rig

In addition, the tip resistance of the T-bar is corrected for the unequal pore pressure effects using the expression:

$$q_{T-bar} = q_c - [u_0(1-\alpha)] \frac{A_s}{A_p} \quad (2)$$

where u_0 is the ambient pore pressure and A_s/A_p is the ratio of the area of the connection of the shaft to the penetrometer and the area of the penetrometer in the plane normal to the shaft. As this ratio is of the order of 0.1, the correction is far less significant than for the CPTU, where the ratio is unity.

A summary of the T-bar and piezoball testing carried out in Ireland, to the knowledge of the author, is given on Table 2.

Figure 30. Full flow probes (a) T-bar and (b) piezoball penetrometer (In Situ Site Investigations Ltd.)

The effect of the pore water pressure correction is illustrated in Figure 31, which shows the percentage corrections for the net CPTU and T-bar resistance at the Portumna site. As can be seen the adjustment to the cone data can be very significant, i.e. up to 17%, compared to an average correction for the T-bar of about 4%. It can also be seen that the T-bar results are very repeatable and appear to produce a smoother profile than the CPTU.

Table 2. Summary of T-bar and piezoball testing carried out on Irish sites

Site	T-bar	Piezoball	Main reference
Athlone Bypass	✓		Long and Gudjonsson (2004)
Loughmore	✓		As above
Portumna	✓		As above
Bogganfin	✓		Donohue (2005)
Bundoran - Ballyshannon	✓		Long and Phoon (2004)
Ennis Bypass	✓		Unpublished UCD Internal Report
Athlone Bypass		✓ (In Situ SI)	Long et al. (2014), Colreavy et al. (2010)
Bunratty Bypass		✓ (In Situ SI)	Long et al. (2014)
M17/ N18 Gort to Tuam		✓ (Lankelma)	As above
Foynes Harbour Access Rd.		✓ (In Situ SI)	Carroll (2013)

Figure 31. CPTU and T-bar data for Portumna site

The ball penetrometer (Figure 30b) was later developed to reduce the chance of the load cell being subjected to bending moments and to minimise risk of buckling of the driving rods. The ball probe is also more compatible with temporary steel casing used offshore. The reader is referred to Randolph (2004) or to DeJong et al. (2010) for further details on these devices. These penetrometers have several advantages over the standard cone (Randolph, 2004):

- As the soil is able to flow around these probes, the overburden pressure is equilibrated above and below the probe except for the area of the shaft. This means that the measured resistance requires minimal adjustment to provide the net resistance compared to a CPTU test.
- Improved accuracy is obtained in soft soils due to the larger projected area that is typically 100 cm² compared to the 10 cm² of the cone. This results in improved resolution and reduced sensitivity to any load cell drift.
- The availability of plasticity solutions based on an ideal perfectly plastic Tresca soil model, which provide upper and lower bound resistance factors relating to s_u , see for example Randolph (2004).

A further recent development has been the inclusion of a pore pressure measuring element in the T-bar and ball (piezoball), Long (2008) provides details of some of these different piezoballs. A significant issue is that there is no standardisation in the design of these instruments, particularly with respect to the location of the pore water pressure transducer, which has variably been included at the tip, mid plane and equator of the ball (Figure 30b). An example of some CPTU and piezoball data from the Bunratty Bypass is shown on Figure 32. Similar data was obtained from the two devices. Again the piezoball data seems somewhat smoother. Care needs to be taken when saturating the piezoball filters.

Much of the early work on these devices has concerned the determination of the undrained shear strength (s_u) and the remoulded undrained shear strength (s_{ur}). However some very interesting recent work on the use of these devices for the purposes of measuring consolidation parameters shows much promise (Mahmoodzadeh et al., 2014, Mahmoodzadeh et al., 2015). Efforts should be made to try out some of these findings on Irish soft soils.

Figure 32. CPTU and piezoball data from Bunratty Bypass

It is also interesting to note that internationally significant contributions on the development of these devices have been made by three Australian based Irish researchers Noel Boylan (NGI Australia), Cathal Colreavy (ARUP Australia) and Con O’Loughlin (University of Western Australia / COFS), (Colreavy et al., 2016a, Colreavy et al., 2016b) and (Boylan et al., 2007, Boylan et al., 2016)

(Seismic) Marchetti Dilatometer Testing (SDMT)

Perhaps the third most widely used modern test worldwide (after the CPTU and pressuremeter) for the purposes of soil characterisation and determination of soil parameters in soft soils is the flat dilatometer (DMT) (Marchetti, 1980). A dilatometer test consists of pushing a flat blade located at the end of a series of rods into the ground, see Figure 33. Once at the testing depth, a circular steel membrane located on one side of the blade is expanded horizontally into the soil. The pressure is recorded at specific moments during the test (p_0 and p_1 on Figure 33).

Figure 33. Marchetti dilatometer and SDMT (www.marchetti-dmt.it)

The blade is then advanced to the next test depth. Various soil parameters can then be derived from these measurements together with knowledge of the in situ effective stress and pore water pressure. The big advantage of the DMT test is that the measurements made are very simple (depth and pressure). No corrections are necessary and the accuracy and resolution of the measurements is very high.

Marchetti et al. (2008) subsequently introduced seismic piezocone (SCPTU) technology into the DMT, by the inclusion of geophones, to form the seismic dilatometer (SDMT). According to Monaco et al. (2014) the “true-interval” two-receiver test configuration results in a high degree of repeatability of the shear wave velocity (V_s) measurements. This system comprises a cylindrical element placed above the DMT blade, equipped with two receivers located at 0.5 m distance. As for the SCPTU the shear wave source at the surface is a pendulum hammer which hits horizontally a rectangular beam pressed vertically against the soil and oriented with its long axis parallel to the axis of the receivers.

Only a limited amount of SDMT testing has been reported for Irish sites, for example for the Limerick Southern Ring Road (Bihs et al., 2010), Foynes (Carroll et al., 2012) and Cork City (Hemmingway and Long, 2011). Unpublished data is also available for Athlone. In each case the results were promising. Clearly the DMT / SDMT is a reliable and adaptable tool and could be considered for use in any project involving soft ground. A possible weakness of the

DMT is that derivation of geotechnical parameters involves the use of empirical correlations, which were developed some time ago, mainly for Italian soils. This is an area which well warrants research.

Advanced drilling rigs

In the Scandinavian countries shell and auger drilling is not used. There use is made of advanced multipurpose drilling rigs, see Figure 34. The rigs are equipped for a wide range of geotechnical investigation methods such as drilling through hard ground or rock, total sounding, weight sounding, rotary pressure sounding, dynamic sounding, SPT, CPTU, field vane testing and sampling. In addition the rigs are fitted with sensors for measuring data such as feed force, rotation speed and torque, hammer pressure, flushing media pressure and depth. Typically the rigs weigh 4t – 5t and are tracked. Much of the control of the rigs is by a remote unit. For the operator there are significant improved health and safety issue related to the use of these rigs over and above older types.

Geophysics - shear wave velocity

General

In the authors experience of working with Norwegian and Swedish soft clays it has been found that the profiles and values of the shear wave velocity (V_s) can be a very powerful signature of the soft soils and can provide valuable design data using correlations between V_s and other related parameters. This experience is applied to Irish soft soils later in the paper. Initially some background to the techniques will be given.

Engineer's interest in V_s determination has largely been driven by the need to obtain values of the small strain shear modulus (G_{max}), as this is an important parameter for a range of geotechnical design applications. This usually involves strains of 10⁻³% and less. According to elastic theory G_{max} may be calculated from the shear wave velocity using the following equation:

$$G_{max} = \rho V_s^2 \quad (3)$$

where G_{max} = shear modulus (Pa), V_s = shear wave velocity (m/s) and ρ = density (kg/m³).

Several techniques are commonly used to measure V_s in both the field or in the laboratory. Intrusive field methods include cross-hole (CH), down-hole and seismic cone / seismic dilatometer (SCPTU / SDMT) methods. In these surveys seismic sources and receivers are located either between boreholes or between the surface and a point in a borehole or cone. Non-intrusive field methods used to determine V_s include seismic reflection and refraction and surface wave surveys (SASW / MASW).

In Ireland there has been extensive use of the Multichannel Analysis of Surface Waves (MASW) methods for the purposes of determining V_s , see Figure 35a. The MASW technique was introduced in the late 1990's by the Kansas Geological Survey (Park et al., 1999). MASW exploits proven multichannel recording and processing techniques that are similar to those used in conventional seismic reflection surveys. For details of the application of the technique to soft soils in Ireland, the reader is referred to Donohue et al. (2004).

Surface waves (Raleigh waves) are usually generated by a blow of a sledge hammer. This generates waves with a wide range of frequencies. As waves of different frequencies relate to different depths (dispersive nature of ground) a phase velocity versus frequency plot (called a dispersion curve) can be produced. By means of inversion of this curve a profile of shear wave velocity versus depth can be developed. In Ireland the software Surfseis is usually used to perform the inversion procedure (Xia et al., 1999).

V_s profiles for Norwegian and Swedish soft soils

Donohue et al. (2004) and Donohue and Long (2008) initially showed that the method works well for Irish soft soils at Athlone, Portumna and Ballinasloe. Subsequently the MASW method has been successfully used to characterise soft soils in various countries such as Norway (L'Heureux and Long, 2017) and Sweden (Long et al., 2017b). Some V_s profiles for these countries are shown on Figure 36.

Figure 34. Advanced drilling rigs (a) from www.geotech.se and (b) use of rig at NTNU's Stjørdal research site

Figure 35. (a) MASW survey at Ballinasloe research site and (b) V_s profiles for Irish soft clay sites

It is important to realise that the surface wave technique, especially MASW, was never designed to give information of boundaries between different soil layers and the underlying stiff soils / bedrock. Great care needs to be taken when attempting to identify such boundaries from V_s data. Its main purpose is to produce engineering design parameters.

The differences between the Swedish and Norwegian results are mainly due to variations in the composition of the material (e.g. water content, unit weight, clay content and organic matter) and also in situ effective stresses.

V_s profiles for Irish soft soils

A limited number of profiles for Irish soft clays are available and these are shown on Figure 35b. See Table A for references and Figure 6 for the location of the sites.

Care needs to be taken when assessing these data, as they are from sites with mixed geological history. Ballinasloe, Bogganfin, Athlone and Portumna are all post glacial lake sites whereas the organic clays from Limerick and Cork are of estuarine origin. Two different techniques were used to obtain the data with SDMT being used at Athlone Profile B, Limerick and Cork and MASW at the remaining sites. It should also be noted that the Athlone Profile B test was undertaken in an area where a 1.5 m layer of fill was placed some 15 years before the testing, whereas the Athlone Profile D MASW data were obtained on undisturbed natural ground. Similarly the Limerick Tunnel data was obtained from a position close to the road embankments and the results may have been influenced by the embankment load.

Figure 36. V_s profiles for (a) selected Norwegian sites and (b) Swedish sites from Long et al. (2107)

Nonetheless the data is relatively consistent with V_s increasing from about 50 m/s at ground level to an average of about 125 m/s at 8 m depth. The values for the Irish sites are similar to those of the Swedish organic clays.

V_s profiles for some Irish silt sites are also available. The values are higher than those for the clays and are also much more scattered. This is due to the nature of the silty soils which contain lenses and layers of sands and other material.

Geophysics – electrical resistivity

The electric resistivity method goes back as far as the early 20th century and was primarily developed to distinguish oil bearing from water bearing layers (Archie, 1942). In general, resistivity (the ability to conduct electrical current) of soils and rocks is a function of porosity, the ion content / salinity of the pore water, clay content and presence of charged minerals such as graphite and some sulphides, Electrical resistivity tomography (ERT) is used extensively in geotechnical investigations in Ireland. In particular, it is used for general site characterisation studies, as a screening tool in the selection of borehole locations, and for sourcing granular material for construction purposes. A particular advantage of ERT in Irish granular soils and boulder clays is that these soils are difficult to characterise by conventional sampling and laboratory testing due to the presences of gravel and cobble sized fragments.

There has been less experience in the use of resistivity for characterising Irish soft compressible soils. However the technique is used extensively in Norway, Sweden and Canada in the investigation of marine clays. Marine clays will have higher resistivity if the salt has been leached from the pore fluid and thus the technique can be used to check if the marine clays are potentially of very high sensitivity or even quick (Long et al., 2017a).

Over the years empirical relationships between measured resistivity and the soil type involved have been developed. An example of some of these relationships is given on Table 3.

A significant recent development in resistivity profiling in North America (mostly used for investigating contaminated ground) and in Scandinavia (mostly used to try to detect quick clays) has been the resistivity cone penetrometer (RCPTU), see Figure 37.

Table 3. Some examples of empirical relationships between soft soil type and resistivity

Soil type	Resistivity value (Ωm)	Country	Reference
Clay	20 – 30	Ireland	O'Connor et al. (2016)
Silty clay	30 – 50		
Clayey sand	Mid 60's?		
Unleached marine deposits	1 - 10	Norway	Solberg et al. (2012)
Leached clay deposits	10 – 80 / 100		
Dry crust, silty deposits	> 80 / 100		

The sounding equipment used for RCPTU consists of an ordinary piezocone (CPTU) probe and a resistivity module mounted behind the probe. Scandinavian manufacturers of RCPTU equipment have chosen to equip their resistivity probes with four ring-electrodes.

Figure 37. RCPTU (www.geotech.se)

The two outer electrodes transmit electric current into the soil, whereas the two inner electrodes measure the difference in potential. The resistivity depth profile is only limited by the maximum borehole penetration depth. The module needs to be regularly calibrated in brine solutions of salt and water to ensure correct readings.

When comparing resistivity measurements, it is important to be aware that these are influenced by a soil volume involving some centimetres (laboratory) to some tens of centimetres for RCPTU, some meters to tens of meters for ERT and finally some tens of meters to some hundreds of meters for airborne electromagnetic methods (AEM). Bearing all these factors in mind, all three methods derive consistent and overlapping information,

SAMPLE DISTURBANCE EFFECTS

Summary of Irish experience

There is considerable experience in Ireland into the effects of sample disturbance on soft compressible soils. Work has been carried out at several sites where the results of laboratory tests on samples recovered using different sampler types have been analysed and compared. A summary of this work, known to the author, is given on Table B (at back of paper).

Sampling disturbance effects on clays

General

There are many studies reported in the literature on sample disturbance effects on clays. Some examples are the classic papers of La Rochelle and Lefebvre (1971) on Champlain Sea clay, Lunne et al. (2006) on Norwegian clays, Hight et al. (1992) on Bothkennar clay from the UK and Tanaka et al. (1996) on Japanese clays. Figure 38 shows the possible stress path for tube sampling a lightly overconsolidated clay as the stress changes from the in situ state (Point 1) to the stress just before laboratory testing (Point 9) (Ladd and DeGroot, 2003). The reduction in stress is as a result of drilling, sampling, transport, storage and handling. The effects of drilling and sampling are particularly pronounced.

Clearly then sampling causes a reduction in effective stress in the samples. Thus if the sample is subjected to a simple quick undrained triaxial tests (UUC in Figure 38) a very low strength value will be obtained. It is necessary to re-consolidate the sample back to its in situ strength in order to try to recover the in situ behaviour.

Figure 38. Possible stress path for a lightly overconsolidated clay during sampling (Ladd and DeGroot, 2003)

The various international studies have also confirmed that poor quality piston tube sampling causes destructureation of the clays leading to:

- lower p'_c ,
 - lower Young's modulus (E) and constrained modulus (M), permeability (k) and coefficient of consolidation (c_v) at small strains,
 - lower u_s ,
 - peak strengths occur at higher strains and strain softening effects less pronounced,
- when compared to values from high quality samples.

The effects on parameters such as large strain compressibility (compression index, C_c or modulus number, m), values of k and c_v at higher strains, creep coefficient (C_{α} , C_{sec} or r_s) or on effective friction angle (ϕ') are less well understood. However the effects are likely to be less than on those parameters listed above.

Figure 39. CRS oedometer test results from Lierstranda (Lunne et al., 1997a)

Effects on oedometer test results

These findings are illustrated in the classic results from a set of constant rate of strain oedometer tests (CRS) from the NGI research site at Lierstranda (near Drammen – some 30 km south-west of Oslo) shown on Figure 39. Samples were taken using the Sherbrooke block sampler and two fixed piston samplers of 75 mm and 54 mm in diameter (Lunne et al., 1997a).

The most significant effects of sample disturbance are to reduce p'_c and the constrained modulus M ($=\Delta\sigma'_v/\Delta\varepsilon$) at stresses less than p'_c . For example the maximum value of M measured on the 54 mm tube sample is some 0.58 times that of the block sample value. Together with the lower value of p'_c that would have been obtained, a considerable overestimation of likely settlement would have been made if the results of the 54 mm samples were used in a settlement analysis compared to that which would have been predicted by the block sample results.

Long (2006b) reports on a series of sixteen incrementally loaded (IL) oedometer tests carried out on samples of Athlone grey organic clay (Figure 12) which were obtained from ELE 30°, ELE 5°, MOSTAP 65 samplers as well as by Sherbrooke block sampling (Figure 24). Typical log σ'_{v0} – strain plots for each of the sampler types are shown on Figure 40a. The block sample and 30° tube tests show a similar response and are of the characteristic rounded shape for an organic material. In

contrast both the 5° and MOSTAP® tests show a much flatter curve, i.e. a stiffer response and it is more difficult to define p'_c . It is recognised that as oedometer tests are on thin specimens, then variations in material type will strongly affect the results. In particular silty soils will give flatter curves.

Of perhaps more interest is to compare the block and 30° tube sample tests with some field compressibility data as shown on Figure 40b.

Figure 40. (a) Results of IL oedometer tests and (b) field behaviour of Athlone grey organic clay

The field data is from Long and O’Riordan (2001). These data were obtained in the field during the construction of two trial embankments (known as the main and subsidiary trials). Magnet extensometers were placed at the top, middle and bottom of the organic clay stratum so therefore field strains were directly obtained. Vertical effective stress was calculated from total stress less pore pressure from piezometers installed in the centre of the organic clay layer. Stress – strain curves can then be constructed to compare with oedometer test results, as shown on Figure 40b.

In the normally consolidated zone, all the field data show similar behaviour and in general indicate a more compressible response than that of the block and 30° specimens (which in turn were more compressible than the MOSTAP 65 and 5° specimens). It is very likely that rate of loading effects contribute to the lower stiffness values measured in the field. Field loading is slower and therefore a more flexible response will result.

Effects on triaxial test results

Some results of anisotropically consolidated undrained triaxial tests (CAUC) on samples of Lierstranda clay are shown on Figure 41. Similar to the oedometer tests, shown on Figure 39, samples were obtained using the Sherbrooke block sampler and two fixed piston samplers.

As discussed above it can be seen the effects of the sampling are to reduce s_u and small strain stiffness (E) to increase strain to failure (ϵ_f) and to reduce strain softening effects. For example s_u from the 54 mm sample is equal to 0.78 that of the block sample. Such a reduction would lead to a conservative design. From a summary of a large database of block samples on Norwegian clays, Karlsrud and Hernandez-Martinez (2013) found that CACU s_u was between 10-50% higher in block samples than for 54 mm piston samples. The corresponding figures for CAUE (extension tests) and DSS (direct simple shear testing) were 0-10% and 5-20% respectively.

Figure 41. CAUC triaxial tests on Lierstranda clay (Lunne et al., 1997a)

In the authors experience the stress path plot shown on Figure 41b is particularly useful in demonstrating the effects of sample disturbance. Here the stress paths are presented in MIT or NGI format in the form of:

$$t' = (\sigma'_a - \sigma'_r) / 2 \text{ versus } s' = (\sigma'_a + \sigma'_r) / 2$$

where: σ'_a is the axial effective stress and σ'_r is the radial effective stress.

According to Lunne et al. (1997a) for a “perfect” specimen, pre-peak, in which there is minimum plastic volumetric strain, the initial stress path (plotted in s' , t' space as here) slope will be 1 horizontal to 3 vertical. An undisturbed specimen will retain this more or less linear stress path until the failure line is reached. The block sample specimen exhibits this behaviour, confirming the sample has retained its structure and is behaving in an “elastic” manner at low strains. For the 54 mm and 75 mm specimens the stress path bends quickly to the left suggesting the samples have lost some of their structure and are disturbed.

Assessment of sample disturbance effects on clays

A variety of methods are available for the assessment of sample disturbance. These include:

- Visual inspection (e.g. bending of layers / varves in sample)
- Radiography (e.g. X-ray) (i.e. use image to select best part of sample for lab testing)
- Examination the shape of the stress / strain curve or stress path plot
- Volumetric strain required to load the sample to its initial effective stress (ε_{v0}) (see Table 4)
- Normalised void ratio change to initial effective stress ($\Delta e/e_0$) (see Table 4)
- Measuring the initial suction / residual effective stress in the soil sample (σ'_s / Point 9 on Figure 38), (Donohue and Long, 2009, Donohue and Long, 2010) or Tanaka and Nishida (2008)
- Comparison of the shear wave velocity measured on a soil sample to that measured in situ, see for example (Landon et al., 2007) or the references listed in the previous bullet point
- Slope of stress path / pore water pressure dilatancy parameter (Lunne et al., 1997a).

The two most common techniques used to assess sample quality are the assessment of ε_{v0} or $\Delta e/e_0$ required to load the sample back to its in situ effective stress (e.g. in an oedometer, triaxial or DSS test), see Table 4. The former criterion has been in use for many years (Andresen and Kolstad, 1979). The latter criterion was first introduced by Lunne et al. (1997a) who argued that $\Delta e/e_0$ is a more reasonable parameter to use, as it is a measure of the change in pore volume to the initial pore volume, while ε_{v0} is equal to the change in pore volume divided by the initial total volume. Lunne et al. (1997a) stated that their criterion was mostly for use in soft to firm marine clays with OCR in the range 1 to 4. De Groot and Ladd (2012) refer to this method as the “gold standard” approach.

Main causes of sample disturbance effects on clays

Many factors influence the quality of soil samples. They can be summarised as follows but the reader is referred to the classic papers of Hvorslev (1949), Kallstenius (1958), Hight (1993) or Hight (2001) for a more details.

Table 4. Sample quality assessment criteria (after Ladd and DeGroot, 2003)

Specimen quality designation (SQD) (Terzaghi et al., 1996)		$\Delta e/e_0$ (Lunne et al., 1997a)		Class	Quality*
ε_{v0} (%)	SQD	$\Delta e/e_0$ for OCR = 1 - 2	$\Delta e/e_0$ for OCR = 2 - 4		
< 1	A	<0.04	<0.03	1	Very good to excellent
1 - 2	B	0.04-0.07	0.03-0.05	2	Good to fair
2 - 4	C	0.07-0.14	0.05-0.1	3	Poor
4 - 8	D	>0.14	>0.1	4	Very poor
> 8	E				

* Refers to use of samples for measurement of mechanical properties

- Sample diameter
- Length / diameter ratio
- Area ratio, see Table 1
- Friction / inside / outside clearance, see Table 1
- Drilling techniques, see Figure 22
- Cutting edge angle, see Table 1
- Transportation
- Extrusion
- Time between sampling and testing
- Trimming
- Net area tested

Research internationally has shown that the cutting edge angle is the key component of the sampler geometry which controls sample quality and that it is not easy to overcome the effects of a poor cutting edge angle by changing the other sampler dimensions (Horng et al., 2010). Clearly it is important to use a sampler with an area ratio and cutting edge angle that satisfies the Eurocode (ENISO, 2006) and to take as much care as possible in transporting, extruding and building in the specimen into the laboratory device. Time between sampling and testing should be minimised (Amundsen and Thakur, 2018). In Ireland the key issue that remains is the effect of the drilling technique on the subsequent sampling, see Figure 22.

Donohue (2005) investigated these effects at the Ballinasloe and Bogganfin test sites by comparing samples obtained using the conventional techniques to those obtained using the Scandinavian “displacement” approach where the sampler is pushed down to the desired depth before sampling without the use of a borehole. He compared the results of testing adjacent samples taken by the conventional approach, by the Scandinavian displacement approach and by U4 technique (Figure 42). Both the piston samples had a 5° cutting edge angle.

Figure 42. Comparison of (a) oedometer tests and (b) triaxial tests for different sampling techniques at Ballinasloe (Donohue, 2005)

In both cases the displacement sample is clearly of higher quality. For the oedometer test the displacement sample has higher p_c' , higher small strain stiffness and more compressible post yield. For the triaxial test the displacement sample has higher s_u , higher small strain stiffness, has lower strain to failure and exhibits clear strain softening post peak. Therefore the results of a design based on the results of the traditional samples or the U4 samples could yield data which is dominated by disturbance effects and not consistent with the in situ behaviour of the soils. More work on this topic is well warranted and the development of the MOSTAP 70 sampler, which does not require a borehole, is an interesting advancement.

Sampling disturbance effects on intermediate soils / silts and laminated soils

For the most part sample disturbance in clay soils results in more conservative design parameters (post yield stiffness may be an exception). Unfortunately sample disturbance in intermediate, low to medium plasticity, clays and silts often has the opposite effect, i.e. can lead to a non-conservative set of parameters. Hight (1993) reviewed the effects of sampling in sands and pointed out that, if the sampling process is drained, both shear and volumetric strains can occur.

Loose sands will compact and dense sands will expand, as a result of dilation. In most cases sampling in clay will be undrained but this may not always be the case in silts. It is important then to assess whether the sampling process in these soils is drained or not.

Long (2006a) discusses these effects for various soils and also reports on a detailed study of work on Athlone brown laminated clay in which the results of testing Sherbooke block, ELE 30°, ELE 5° (both using conventional boring) and MOSTAP 65 samples are compared.

Normalised deviator stress / strain plots for four selected CAUC triaxial tests are shown on Figure 43a. There is a significant difference in behaviour between the tube samples and the block samples. It can be seen that the 30° and 5° specimens appear more ductile with peak strengths occurring at about 6% strain and with only a moderate degree of strain softening post peak. Behaviour of the block samples is quite brittle, with peak strength occurring at less than 1% strain and with considerable strain softening being evident. The block sample shows much lower s_u than the other samples. The MOSTAP® test result shows clear evidence of disturbance.

The difference in behaviour is perhaps most clear in the stress path plots on Figure 43b. The block sample test initially shows clear structure and contracts in the manner expected for lightly overconsolidated clays.

Figure 43. CAUC triaxial test results for Athlone brown laminated clay (Long, 2006a)

There is a marked difference in the behaviour of the tube specimens in that they initially contract but post-peak there is a strong tendency for dilative behaviour, with that of the 5° specimens being more marked than for the 30° samples. The MOSTAP® test results are erratic.

It would seem this sample has been severely destructured. A line representing a Mohr-Coulomb strength of $\phi' = 36^\circ$ and $c' = 0$ (critical state line for the block samples) has also been plotted on the figure. Long (2006a) concluded that both destructuration and densification effects had occurred during the tube sampling. Because of the laminated nature of the material, it is possible that sample tube insertion is a partially drained process. This would result in drainage of excess pore pressure from the silt layers during tube insertion, causing a contraction of these layers with a corresponding densification of the material.

Inspection of the fragile microstructure of the brown laminated clay (Figure 5) confirms the feasibility of the destructuration and densification of this material by tube sampling.

Long (2006a) concluded that the sample disturbance effects observed above for Athlone brown laminated clay, i.e. resulting in non-conservative design parameters, can occur in materials where the clay content is less than 40% or the I_p is less than 20%. Careful assessment needs to be made of laboratory tests on tube samples of these soils.

Carroll (2013) carried out a comprehensive study of Irish silts from Skibbereen, Foynes and Letterkenny. As part of her work she compared the results of laboratory tests on hand carved block samples of silt from Letterkenny to those on piston samples. The piston tube sample tubes had a cutting edge angle of about 10° (Table 1). A relatively fast sampling rate of approximately 10 cm/s was used in an attempt to minimise drainage. Carroll and Long (2017) concluded that the piston sampling at Letterkenny was largely undrained, with resulting good quality piston tube samples. Results of oedometer, triaxial, direct simple shear and shear wave velocity testing showed that for Letterkenny the quality of piston tube and block samples were identical and that both sets of samples would yield very similar design parameters.

However for the silt at Skibbereen, it seems clear that drainage and densification of the samples occurred during piston sampling despite good quality tubes being used and a relatively fast sampling rate. Clay content was particularly low for this site. The resulting laboratory tests yield non-conservative design parameters i.e. the material appears to be stronger and stiffer than it is in situ.

Conclusions for sample disturbance effects

- All sampling reduces considerably the effective stress in a sample and these stresses should be restored in the lab prior to carrying out testing.
- Shell and auger drilling techniques can cause severe disturbance to the material beneath the base of the borehole, particularly when drilling mud is not used to stabilise the hole.
- Use of the Scandinavian “displacement” approach can help to overcome these effects. The advent of the MOSTAP 70 sampler is an interesting development in

this regard and a trial in Irish soft soils is well warranted.

- In clays sampling causes destructuration of the material, which leads for the most part to a reduction in various parameters such as s_u and small strain stiffness. Conservative designs would result if the disturbed sample parameters were used.
- In intermediate soils, laminated soils or silts the opposite effects can happen. In these soils sampling can cause destructuration and densification resulting in increased s_u and small strain stiffness, i.e. non-conservative design parameters.
- For piston sampling only the best available sample tubes should be used, i.e. those with a thin wall, low area ratio and a sharp cutting edge angle. Every effort should be made to keep the piston stationary during the work.

SOIL CHARACTERISATION

Use of CPTU to determine soil behaviour type (SBT)

Traditional approach – clay soils

As pointed out by Robertson and Cabal (2009) CPTU charts may not provide accurate predictions of soil type based on grain size distribution but can provide a guide to the mechanical characteristics of the soil, or the soil behaviour type (SBT). Use of the CPTU for determining SBT has now gained world-wide acceptance. A number of well-established SBT type charts exist.

Generally these charts use a combination of corrected cone resistance (q_c), sleeve friction (f_s) and pore water pressure (u_2) data or derived parameters such as pore pressure parameter (B_q) and friction ratio (R_f) where:

$$R_f = \left(\frac{f_s}{q_t} \right) \times 100\% \quad (4)$$

$$B_q = \text{pore pressure parameter} = \frac{u_2 - u_0}{q_t - \sigma_{v0}} \quad (5)$$

u_0 = in situ pore pressure

σ_{v0} = total overburden stress

Various authors such as Mollé (2005) and Long (2008) have reviewed the use, accuracy and popularity of SBT charts. Undoubtedly those of Robertson et al. (1986) and Robertson (1990) are the most popular and widely used. The 1986 chart is based on the use of q_c , B_q and R_f as will be described below. The 1990 version is similar to that of 1986 but uses normalised parameters and is intended mostly for deep strata both onshore and offshore.

CPTU data for the Clonmore Link Road (see Figure 15) are shown on Figure 44 (see also

Figure 27a). Here three tests, located near the River Brosna towards the centre of the site, from the 2004 investigation by Fugro are shown. Note that the pore pressure measurements are in the u_1 position rather than the standard u_2 location (Lunne et al., 1997b). There is very good consistency in the data from the three tests. The results clearly identify the three strata. The peat is clearly identified by the high R_f and low u_1 values and the soft clay / silt by the low R_f and relatively high u_1 values.

Figure 44. Clonmore Link Road
- CPTU data

Figure 45. Clonmore Road - Robertson et al. (1986) soil behaviour chart

Data for test CPTU4 from Figure 44 are plotted on the Robertson et al. (1986) SBT chart on Figure 45. The chart also identifies clearly the three strata and correctly predicts the behaviour of the calc marl and soft clay / silt. The calc marl and clay / silt materials generally fall in Zone 3 suggesting they will behave as a “clay”.

The classification seems consistent with the fact that the calc marl is more organic and the silt / clay has slightly higher OCR. The chart does not work well for the peat. The data falls across a range of zones. This is a common result for Irish organic material.

Care needs to be taken when using automatically driven computer software to output strata types from CPTU data. However if the data are plotted in a manner like that shown on Figure 44 (i.e. with high Rf values revealing peat) a more useful representation of the data can be obtained.

Figure 46. Onsøy CPTU data plotted on the Robertson et al. (1986) soil behaviour chart

Figure 47. CPTU data for Foynes (Carroll, 2013)

Some data for the Onsøy site Figure 27b and Figure 28 are plotted on the Robertson et al. (1986) SBT chart on Figure 46. The tests chosen were carried out by two different organizations both using a 10 cm² cone. These were at NGI grid locations B5 and A4, which are 2.1 m apart (Gauer et al., 2002). Test A4 suggests the material is in Behaviour Zone 3 (clay) which is correct. According to the q_t / B_q chart Test B5 also places the material in Zone 3. However the q_t / R_f chart for this test places the material in Zone 1 (sensitive fine grained). Although the Onsøy site is highly uniform this clearly highlights the difficulties in measuring f_s in soft clays and in classifying soil based on R_f values only.

Overall for clayey or silty clay soils the Robertson et al. (1986) SBT charts work well in Irish conditions. The focus should be on q_t and B_q chart. The difficulties with obtaining reliable f_s values are of significant importance and therefore the q_t / R_f chart should be treated with caution. There seems to be a particular problem with characterising highly organic soils and especially peat.

Traditional approach – silt soils

Some CPTU data for the Foynes Harbour Access Road site (Figure 20 and Figure 21) are shown on Figure 47, see Carroll (2013) and Carroll et al. (2012). A number dissipation tests were carried out during the testing and these points are designated by an ‘X’ in Figure 47. Values are quiet variable in the upper sandy silt with large q_t values, greater than 2 MPa, being evident. In the lower clay silt the q_t increases steadily from about 0.3 MPa to about 0.6 MPa with depth. The B_q and u_2 values are low in the upper layer but increase significantly in the lower layer with an average B_q of about 0.9. Normalised friction ratio (F_r , see Formula 9) values show a similar pattern to q_t .

The data for test F01 are plotted on the (Robertson et al., 1986) SBT chart on Figure 48. The charts do separate clearly the three layers involved. The lower clayey silt and the transitional layer are classified in either zones 1 (“sensitive fine grained soil”) or 3 (“clay”). The data for the upper sandy silt falls across a wide range of zones and for the most part the charts are not helpful.

Figure 48. Robertson et al (1986) SBT chart for Foynes

Normalised CPTU data

As has been explained previously Robertson (1990) developed a series of normalised CPTU SBT charts which were mostly intended for deeper soil sequences. Subsequently in an effort to simplify the application of CPTU SBT charts Robertson (2009) suggested the normalised cone parameters Q_t and F_r be combined into one Soil Behaviour Type index (I_c), where I_c is the radius of the essentially concentric circles that represent the boundaries between each SBT zone. I_c can be defined as follows:

$$I_c = \sqrt{(3.47 - \log Q_t)^2 + (\log F_r + 1.22)^2} \quad (6)$$

where:

$$Q_t = \text{normalised cone resistance} = \frac{q_t - \sigma_{v0}}{\sigma_{v0}} \quad (7)$$

$$F_r = \text{normalised friction ratio (expressed as a \%)} \\ = \frac{f_s}{q_t - \sigma_{v0}} \quad (8)$$

Robertson (2009) assigned particular ranges of I_c values to different zones / soil behaviour types, e.g. if $I_c > 3.6$ the SBT is an “organic clay or peat”, for I_c between 2.95 and 3.6 the SBT is “silty clay to clay” etc.

I_c values for the Clonmore Road and Foynes sites are shown on Figure 49. As has been shown the chart works well for characterising the calc marl and the silt / clay at Clonmore Road but fails to accurately characterise the peat. For Foynes the technique nicely separates the two silt layers and characterises them correctly.

Development of alternative soil behaviour chart for intermediate soils

Schneider et al. (2008) proposed SBT charts based on Q_t and $\Delta u_2 / \sigma_{v0}'$. These parameters were chosen so as to separate the influences of yield stress ratio and partial consolidation on normalised CPTU parameters.

Figure 49. I_c values for (a) Foynes and (b) Clonmore Road. The charts were developed from a combination of large strain finite element analyses of undrained cone penetration, cavity expansion modelling of pore pressure

generation, data from variable rate CPTU tests together with a relatively large database of field testing. The resulting proposed chart in semi log $Q_t - \Delta u_2 / \sigma_{v0}'$ space is shown on Figure 50 with data for Foynes. The SBT chart works very well and clearly separates the upper sandy silt (which is mostly classified as a “silt or intermediate soil”) from the lower clayey silt (which is classified as “undrained clay”). Information in this form would be very useful to a designer for example facing a decision on whether vertical drains were necessary or not.

Figure 50. Schneider et al. (2008) SBT chart for Foynes

In the opinion of the author the big advantages of this chart are that it is “clean” and does not contain too many zones and that it uses the more reliable u_2 data rather than the more uncertain f_s readings. A disadvantage is that organic soils are not considered. However it is recommended that the three approaches described above are applied when attempting to characterise Irish soft soils using CPTU data.

Use of SDMT for soil characterisation

It is also possible to characterise the SBT using data from DMT or SDMT. The three key DMT derived parameters are the material index I_D , the horizontal stress index K_D and the dilatometer modulus E_D expressed by a combination of p_1 and p_0 (the first and second pressure reading), see Figure 33, as follows:

$$I_D = \frac{p_1 - p_0}{p_0 - u_0} \quad (9)$$

$$K_D = \frac{p_0 - u_0}{\sigma'_{v0}} \quad (10)$$

$$E_D = 34.7(p_1 - p_0) \quad (11)$$

I_D is related to the rigidity index of the material, K_D is dependent on the coefficient earth pressure at rest K_0 and E_D is a function of the stiffness of the soil. Note that little work has been done to establish K_0 of Irish compressible soils except for a limited application of the pressurimeter at the Athlone and Kinnegar (Belfast) sites (Powell, 2008).

Figure 51 shows the SBT chart, based on I_D and E_D , for the Foynes site (Marchetti and Crapps, 1981). The chart works well in separating out the three different layers. Perhaps the data for the transitional layer and part of the lower layer falls too low in the chart and are classified incorrectly. However use of the chart or some derivation of the chart has some promise.

The chart works well in separating out the three different layers. Perhaps the data for the transitional layer and part of the lower layer falls too low in the chart and are classified incorrectly. However use of the chart or some derivation of the chart has some promise. In particular if V_s data is also available from SDMT testing some valuable information can be obtained on the site characterisation (see next section). Bihs et al. (2010) showed that the SDMT data was useful for characterising soils on the Limerick Southern Bypass project. Although use of the test shows some promise additional work is required before any definitive conclusions can be made as to its application to Irish soft soils.

Figure 51. SDMT soil behaviour type chart for Foynes

Use of geophysics for site characterisation

Shear wave velocity

Shear wave velocity values can be a powerful means of characterising sites and in particular showing variations across a site or from one site to another.

A clear example of this lies in a comparison of the data from the Athlone Profile D and Bogganfin sites which are located some 200 m from one another and where the geological history is the same. The Bogganfin site is situated on the south side of the Athlone Bypass, see Figure 10.

As can be seen on Figure 35b, the V_s values for Bogganfin are more or less twice those from Athlone. Results of index testing for Bogganfin are shown on Figure 52 and should be compared to those at Athlone Profile D on Figure 12. Note the same scales have been used in both figures. At Bogganfin a thin layer of peat / organic soil overlies brown laminated clay which overlies a lower soft silt. The grey organic clay underlying the Athlone Bypass site is not present probably indicating a fairly complex sequence of erosion surfaces during post - glacial times. In contrast to Athlone the properties of the materials are relatively consistent with depth with an average water content of some 35%, bulk density of 2 Mg/m³ and a plasticity index of some 10%. The lower water content and higher bulk density values when compared to Athlone are consistent with the higher V_s values at this site.

UNDRAINED SHEAR STRENGTH

General

Although s_u is one of the most used and useful property in soil mechanics, it is a difficult parameter. There is no one unique value for s_u for a particular piece of soil. It depends on, amongst many factors, anisotropy, test type, effective stress, stress history, rate of loading and temperature effects.

The influence of anisotropy / test type is shown on Figure 53 for an infinite slope stability problem and for an embankment on soft ground. The soil along the potential sliding surface in the infinite slope stability problem is mostly in direct simple shear (DSS). In contrast that beneath the embankment is partly also in compression (anisotropically consolidated undrained tests - CAUC) and partly in extension (CAUE). average s_u .

A summary of the anisotropy strength ratios observed on high quality block samples of Norwegian clay is given on Table 5. Anisotropy strength ratios for Norwegian clays (Lunne et al., 2006) (Lunne et al., 2006). It would seem that the results of the DSS testing may give approximately the average s_u .

Table 5. Anisotropy strength ratios for Norwegian clays (Lunne et al., 2006)

Anisotropy ratio	Mean	Number of samples	Regression coefficient, R ²
$s_{u,DSS}/s_{u,CAUC}$	0.69	20	0.989
$s_{u,CAUE}/s_{u,CAUC}$	0.42	19	0.985

Figure 52. Bogganfin site
 (a) water content,
 (b) bulk density and
 (c) plasticity index

Figure 53. Influence of anisotropy / test type on s_u

There has been little work done on the effect of rate and temperature on the results of laboratory strength testing of Irish soil. For Norwegian clays, Lunne et al. (2006) report that the rate effect is such that on average the s_u value will increase by 9.4% per log cycle of change of rate. Berre et al. (2007) show that a decrease in the testing temperature will result in an increase in the measured p_c' and s_u values. It is possible that the effects of rate and temperature may compensate for one another.

As regards the effects of stress and stress history Ladd and Foott (1974) proposed that s_u be expressed in a normalised form (s_u/σ_v') in relation to the overconsolidation ratio (OCR) as follows:

$$\frac{s_u}{\sigma_v'} = S(OCR)^m \quad (12)$$

The principal behind this approach was called the SHANSEP procedure. Although it was strictly speaking developed for tests on artificially overconsolidated clays, Karlsrud and Hernandez-Martinez (2013) considered that the same framework could be used for work on s_u values derived from high quality samples. These authors found that on average for Norwegian clays:

- CAUC: $S = 0.30$, $m = 0.70$
- CAUE: $S = 0.12$, $m = 0.80$
- DSS: $S = 0.22$, $m = 0.80$

Figure 54. Results of CAUC tests on Irish clays against (a) water content (b) in situ vertical effective stress

Undrained shear strength from laboratory testing of Irish soft soils

CUAC tests

The data considered here are those on the best quality samples only (i.e. those on block samples or those on sample tubes with a sharp cutting edge). Also soils which behave in a “clay” like manner only are considered. This means for example that the data from CPTU testing should fall in or near the “clay” zone on the SBT charts and / or have a B_q value greater than 0.3 (Mayne, 2007).

In all of the tests considered here the samples were reconsolidated anisotropically to the best estimate of the in situ stress prior to shearing (CAUC). The results are plotted in the normalised s_u/σ_{v0}' form against water content on Figure 54a and against σ_{v0}' on Figure 54b.

The plots suggest that s_u/σ_{v0}' increases with increasing water content. However it is possible that this trend is dominated by the results for the Athlone grey organic clay and there is significant scatter at a water content of about 40%. Other authors have presented the data on Figure 54a plotted against plasticity index. No trend was observed for the Irish soils and considerable scatter is observed when the data are plotted in this way. The data are plotted against σ_{v0}' on Figure 54b in order to try to bring in the effects of stress history / overconsolidation.

It can be seen that s_u/σ_{v0}' decreases with increasing σ_{v0}' as would be expected. It would seem that a s_u/σ_{v0}' value of 0.3 is a robust cautious estimate for CAUC tests on Irish clays. This value is consistent for the SHANSEP results for Norwegian clays with OCR close to 1.0.

CAUE tests

Only limited high quality CAUE triaxial tests are available for Irish soils. For example for the Limerick Tunnel project an average s_u/σ_{v0}' of 0.23 was obtained. For Athlone clay an average s_u/σ_{v0}' of 0.37 was obtained, which is higher than expected from previous SHANSEP work. Further work would be required to investigate these results in more detail.

DSS tests

Results of DSS testing on Norwegian clays and Irish clays are shown on Figure 55. For the Norwegian clays all the samples involved are Sherbrooke block samples and all the tests were undertaken at NGI (Karlsrud and Hernandez-Martinez, 2013). Thus the quality of the samples and testing is very high. The DSS samples were consolidated to the best estimate of the in situ stress.

For the Irish clays a variety of consolidation stresses were used, therefore the results are plotted to the ratio of the consolidation stress to the in situ stress ($\sigma_{vc}'/\sigma_{v0}'$). Unfortunately only a limited number of tests on the best quality samples are available (Foynes and Letterkenny).

Therefore all available data have been shown. All the tests were carried out at UCD with the exception of those on Clonmore Road which were carried out at TCD. For the Norwegian clays there is a strong link between s_u/σ_{v0}' and consolidation stress and beyond a consolidation stress of about 60 kPa the relationship is close to linear at an lower bound value of about 0.22 consistent with the SHANSEP approach.

The effect of stress history / OCR is clear in the Irish data. However in the normally consolidated zone, beyond a $\sigma_{vc}'/\sigma_{v0}'$ value of about 1.5, s_u/σ_{v0}' becomes almost linear and again the average s_u/σ_{v0}' is close to the expected 0.22 value.

UU tests

Not only are UU tests often carried out on disturbed samples the stress remaining in the sample after sampling, transportation, storage, laboratory procedures etc. is likely to be very low and to be some random value (Figure 38). Therefore the resulting s_u value on shearing will be very low and will be meaningless as it refers to some random stress. These tests are of no value and should be discontinued and replaced by fewer high quality CUAC tests. Some argue that the procedure is a useful “index” type test. However there are much better equivalent index shear strength tests such as the Swedish fall cone test.

Figure 55. DSS test results for (a) Norwegian clays and (b) Irish clay. Note Limerick NDR refers to some preliminary investigations for the Limerick Northern Distributary Road. This project is not listed in Table A as only limited data exists

Undrained shear strength from CPTU

For CPTU tests s_u is normally determined by dividing the net cone resistance (q_{net}) by a cone factor (N_{kt}) using Equation 14.

$$s_u = \frac{q_{net}}{N_{kt}} = \frac{(q_t - \sigma_{vo})}{N_{kt}} \quad (13)$$

Given the reliability of the measured pore water pressure in CPTU testing it has become popular to use the excess pore water pressure and another empirical factor $N_{\Delta u}$:

$$s_u = \frac{\Delta u}{N_{\Delta u}} = \frac{u_2 - u_0}{N_{\Delta u}} \quad (14)$$

Although theoretical solutions for N_{kt} and $N_{\Delta u}$ exist, conventional practice is to use empirically derived factors. For example, Karlsrud et al. (1996) and Karlsrud et al. (2005) developed CPTU correlations for Norwegian clays based on carefully executed CPTU tests and laboratory CAUC triaxial tests on high quality block samples. They concluded that $N_{\Delta u}$ gives the best and most consistent results and they found that N_{kt} data is somewhat more scattered.

Data from Karlsrud et al. (1996) is superimposed on the Irish data on Figure 56. Again, as above, only the best quality Irish samples are used. It is important to note that both the Norwegian and Irish data are related to CAUC s_u values. The fit between the two sets of data is very good, albeit the Norwegian data spans a lower range of B_q values. N_{kt} decreases with increasing B_q and $N_{\Delta u}$ increases with increasing B_q as expected.

A best fit line has been added to the N_{kt} / B_q plot. A relatively strong correlation coefficient (R^2) of 0.82 was obtained. There seems to be good promise in the use of such an approach to determine s_u (CAUC) from CPTU.

It would be very useful to perform a similar exercise for DSS test results. However too few high quality test results exist at present for such work to be carried out in a meaningful manner.

Correlations between V_s and undrained shear strength

It is logical to follow a section on s_u from CPTU testing with one on s_u derived from V_s measurements as in modern day CPTU testing it is also possible to obtain a continuous profile of V_s with depth using the seismic piezocone (SCPTU). According to Hardin (1978) the empirical equation describing the influence of the controlling factors on small strain stiffness G_{max} ($=\rho V_s^2$) can be written as follows:

$$G_{max} = A \frac{OCR^k}{F(e)} p_a^{1-n} \sigma_0' \quad (15)$$

where A is a dimensionless parameter characterising the nature of the soil, $F(e)$ is a void ratio function, k is a parameter relating to plasticity index, p_a is atmospheric pressure, n is a parameter dealing with the influence of stress and σ_0' is the in situ stress.

The well-known (Ladd and Foott, 1974) "SHANSEP" equation for normalised undrained shear strength is given above (Equation 12). It can be seen that both V_s and s_u are linked by the same controlling factors and it thus seems possible that there may be a strong link between these two parameters and other geotechnical properties.

Building on this L'Heureux and Long (2017) have shown that there is a very good relationship between V_s and s_u for Norwegian clays as can be seen on Figure 57. Again only high quality block samples were considered and the relationship between V_s and s_u is strong for both CAUC and DSS tests.

Long et al. (2017b) also studied Swedish soft clays and found that, although the link between V_s and the other properties is very good, local correlations are necessary, i.e. the best fit formulae derived for Norwegian clays does not necessarily apply to Swedish clays. A similar finding is made for the Irish clays as shown on Figure 58.

Figure 56. N_{kt} and $N_{\Delta u}$ values for Irish clays corresponding to s_u from CAUC tests

Figure 57. Relationship between V_s and s_u for Norwegian clays CAUC and (b) DSS (L'Heureux and Long, 2017)

Figure 58. Relationship between s_u (CAUC) and V_s for Irish soft clays

Unfortunately only a limited database of V_s values and parallel laboratory tests on good quality samples exists for Irish soft clays. Data is available for Athlone, Ballinasloe, Bogganfin, Portumna and the lower layer at Foynes only.

Although the fit is not as strong as for the Norwegian clays (or Swedish clays) the results are encouraging. More work in this area is well warranted, particularly as SCPTU testing is now widely available and as good results have been obtained for Irish glacial tills and peat. A good relationship between s_u obtained from CIUC (isotropically consolidated) triaxial tests on Irish glacial tills, recovered using the GeoboreS rotary triple tube coring technique, and V_s determined from MASW Irish glacial till was reported by Long et al. (2013). Similarly Trafford (2017) found a strong relationship between s_u (DSS) on hand carved block samples of peat and V_s obtained using a specially designed probe.

Undrained shear strength from full flow probes

It is possible to obtain s_u from full flow probes in a similar manner to that for the CPTU. Net resistance for the T-bar and ball is normally calculated using (Randolph, 2004):

$$q_{T\text{-bar}} \text{ or } q_{\text{Ball}} = q_m - [\sigma_{vo} - (1-a)u_0] \frac{A_s}{A_p} \quad (16)$$

where A_s/A_p is the ratio of shaft area to the bearing area of the probe, which is typically about 0.1 and q_m is the measured resistance. The undrained shear strength is then determined for the T-bar and for the ball by:

$$s_u = \frac{q_{T\text{-bar}}}{N_{T\text{-bar}}} \quad (17)$$

$$s_u = \frac{q_{\text{Ball}}}{N_{\text{Ball}}} \quad (18)$$

where $N_{T\text{-bar}}$ and N_{Ball} are bearing capacity factors for the T-bar and Ball.

Plasticity solutions based on simplified assumptions of soil behaviour were initially used for determination of $N_{T\text{-bar}}$ and N_{Ball} . Typically values of 10.5 and 12 are used respectively.

Based on empirical evidence Lunne et al. (2005) suggest $N_{T\text{-bar}}$ in the range 8-11 corresponding to CAUC s_u and 10-13 corresponding to s_u from DSS tests. DeJong et al. (2011) summarised values for a good number of well characterised international sites and found a range of between 5.9 and 12 corresponding to CAUC tests. It would seem that due to a number of complicating factors such as strain rate effects, strain softening and material anisotropy, it is necessary to empirically derive local bearing capacity factors for use with full flow probes.

An attempt at such a derivation is shown on Figure 59a. The relationship between $N_{T\text{-bar}}$ and B_q is very good and the best fit relationship shows an R^2 value of 0.79. The theoretical value of 10.5 corresponds approximately to the average of the results.

Figure 59. T-bar and ball bearing capacity factors (N_{T-bar} and N_{Ball}) corresponding to s_u (CAUC)

Although this result shows promise there does not seem to be a significant advantage over using N_{kt} as discussed above.

There are fewer reported N_{Ball} values in the literature. For example, DeJong et al. (2011) determined values in the range 7.0 to 12.3 for five well characterised sites internationally and Boylan et al. (2007) reported N_{Ball} (CAUC) values of between 9.9 to 14.7 for Bothkennar clay. To the author's knowledge there are only two sites in Ireland where high quality laboratory test results and ball data are available, i.e. Athlone and Foynes. The resulting N_{Ball} values are shown on Figure 59b. The limited amount of data available have an average close to the theoretical N_{Ball} values of 12.

It is also possible to attempt to determine s_u from the piezoball pore pressure data. Unfortunately the data from Athlone is for a ball with a mid-face pore pressure sensor and that for Foynes has a filter either at the equator or the tip of the ball. Hence such an exercise has not been attempted. However there could be some promise in this approach especially as the coefficient of consolidation (c_h) can also be estimated from these tests.

Undrained shear strength from field vane tests

Some discussion on s_u from field vane data has been already given above (e.g. Figure 25). In the author's opinion great care needs to be taken when interpreting these data due to effects such as that of partial drainage, anisotropy and vane insertion disturbance.

Some vane s_u data from Athlone and Portumna are shown on Figure 60. A variety of techniques were used. In both cases the values in the upper layers seem reasonable. However the values from the lower layers, particularly the brown laminated clay at Athlone, seem very low. Many of the values fall well below the line representing $0.2\sigma_{v0}'$. Some disturbance effects are suspected here.

Undrained shear strength from back-analysis of full scale field failures

To the author's knowledge five full-scale embankment failures on Irish soft ground have been reported in the literature. Two of these were at Athlone, two at Fort Henry embankment and one at the Loughmore Link Road.

Figure 60. s_u from shear vanes at (a) Athlone Profile D and (b) Portumna

Figure 61. Athlone subsidiary trial embankment (Dauncey et al., 1987)

At Athlone a failure was deliberately induced in the case of the subsidiary trial embankment, see Dauncey et al. (1987). Failure occurred at a fill thickness of about 3.0 m (Figure 61). The measured failure surface was non circular in nature, with at least half of its length being located in the brown laminated clay. Dauncey et al. (1987) used conventional limit state stability analysis to back analyse the slip. They found that the peat and the marl contributed only an estimated 5% and 12% respectively to the strength of the embankment's foundation. Best fit between the measured and calculated failure surfaces was found if the strength of the grey organic clay and brown laminated clay were assumed to be equal to $s_u/\sigma_v' = 0.3$ to 0.35 and $s_u/\sigma_v' = 0.2$ to 0.25 respectively. Dauncey et al. (1987) concluded that these values are consistent with the laboratory test results and that the vane test considerably underestimates the operational undrained shear strength of the brown laminated clay.

O'Riordan (1997) and Long and O'Riordan (2000) report on the failure of the east abutment berm at Athlone (Figure 62). Here failure occurred at a fill height of some 1.7 m to 2.0 m. Again a significant portion of the slip surface was in the brown laminated clay and a back-analysis estimated that the operational strength of this material again corresponded to $s_u/\sigma_v' = 0.2$ to 0.25 .

Figure 62. Failure of east abutment berm at Athlone (Long and O'Riordan, 2000)

At the Loughmore Link site (ground conditions are shown on Figure 25b) the failure occurred when an additional 0.5 m of surcharge loading was being placed on an existing layer of fill 2.7 m thick (Long et al., 2007). The failure manifested itself as a series of mostly longitudinal cracks in the surface of the fill (Figure 63). Some cracking perpendicular to the line of the road was also observed. These cracks were up to 750 mm deep. Bulging was apparent in the fields on both sides of the road. Displacement, including shearing of the fence line was observed. The back-analysed shear strength profile was very similar to that given by the field vane results of Contractor 2 and UCD (Figure 25b).

The 1948 downstream slope failure at Fort Henry embankment was attributed to high excess pore pressures due to heavy rainfall (Harty, 1953). An 80 m long section of the Fort Henry embankment failed due to rapid drawdown of the impounded reservoir during June 1979 (Casey et al., 2002). The water level in the reservoir, at the time of the failure was the lowest for some 35 years. Investigations revealed that the failure plane was non-circular in shape and formed through the embankment fill and into the underlying soft silty clay layer.

Ground conditions at the site are complicated (Figure 17 to Figure 19) and an effective stress analysis with computed excess pore water pressures was necessary to explain the reasons for the slide.

Figure 63. Embankment failure at Loughmore Link Road (Long et al., 2007b)

1D COMPRESSION PARAMETERS

General

In a conventional incrementally loaded (IL) oedometer test the load on the sample is maintained for 24 hours prior to a new load being applied. Data for the loading increment are plotted either to the square root of time or to log of time, see for example

Figure 64. The basis for analysing these data lies in the Terzaghi (1925) theory of 1D consolidation. Terzaghi derived an equation relating the excess pore water pressure (u_e) in the soil sample (or consolidating soil layer in the field) to distance from the drainage boundary (z) and time (t) as follows:

$$\frac{k}{\gamma_w m_v} \frac{\partial^2 u_e}{\partial z^2} = \frac{\partial u_e}{\partial t} \quad (19)$$

$$m_v = \frac{1}{M} = \frac{\delta \varepsilon}{\delta \sigma'} \quad (20)$$

where:

k = coefficient of permeability

m_v = coefficient of volume compression

M = constrained modulus

$\delta \varepsilon$ = change in strain

$\delta \sigma'$ = change in effective stress

For simplicity Terzaghi wrote equation as:

$$c_v \frac{\partial^2 u_e}{\partial z^2} = \frac{\partial u_e}{\partial t} \quad (21)$$

where:

c_v is the coefficient of consolidation (m^2/yr)

It is important to realise that c_v is a composite parameter and is stress dependent. Despite its apparent simplicity c_v is one of the most difficult and, in the case of compression of soft ground, one of the most important parameters in soil mechanics. Various methods are available to determine c_v , e.g. that of Taylor (1948) (Figure 64a)

It is also possible to estimate the creep parameter (C_{sec}) from the results of each load increment (Figure 64b) change in strain per log cycle of time and needs to be distinguished from C_α which is the change in void ratio per log cycle of time

$$C_{\text{sec}} = \frac{\Delta \varepsilon}{\Delta \log t} \quad (22)$$

$$C_\alpha = \frac{\Delta e}{\Delta \log t} = (1 + e_0) C_{\text{sec}} \quad (23)$$

Figure 64. Results from a loading increment (196.2 kPa) on a block sample of Onsøy clay in (a) root time and (b) log time formats

It is clear that a standard 24 hour load cycle, such as that shown on

Figure 64, will contain primary compression and some creep. In order to eliminate the effects of creep on the subsequent stress / strain plot, the Scandinavian approach is to carry out shorter load increments, typically of 2 to 3 hours. This has the added advantage in a much faster test.

Subsequently the results of all the load increments are presented in the form of a stress / strain diagram. An example for a high quality Japanese sampler specimen of Onsøy clay is shown on Figure 65 (24 hour load increments). Conventionally the data is plotted in $\log \sigma'_v$ versus ϵ form as shown. However Janbu (1963) and Janbu (1969) suggested that the use of log scales masks the true material behavior and that also in order to fully understand the tests all the data should be plotted in natural scales, i.e. M , c_v and C_{sec} versus σ'_v . The non-linear stress dependent nature of these parameters is very important to understand, i.e. no single value of M , m_v or c_v applies to a particular soil.

Figure 65. IL oedometer test on Onsøy clay: stress versus strain, M , c_v and C_{sec}

Janbu argued that initially around σ'_{v0} the values of M and c_v will be high and that C_{sec} will be low. Then gradually as load is applied and the structure of the material breaks down the values of M and c_v will decrease and C_{sec} will increase and these will reach a minimum / maximum around the preconsolidation stress, p_c' . The value of p_c' obtained in this way is often slightly larger than that obtained using the classical Casagrande (1936) technique.

In practice world-wide the three most popular techniques for determining p_c' are arguably those of Casagrande and Janbu as discussed above together with the work criterion technique of Becker et al. (1987).

Maintained incremental loading (IL) or constant rate of strain testing?

In order to separate out the effects of creep and primary compression, so as to facilitate faster testing and in order to produce more data so a clear set of M and c_v versus σ'_v can be made, constant rate of strain (CRS) testing is common in many countries, e.g. in Scandinavia, see Figure 66 (Sällfors, 1975).

Figure 66. Typical CRS test apparatus (Sällfors, 1975)

The sample is allowed to drain upwards only so that the pore pressure at the base of the sample can be measured (u_b). For the CRS test, the main problem is to choose a suitable rate of strain. Usually the ratio $\Delta u_b / \Delta \sigma'_v$ is used to control the test. In the ASTM standard (ASTM, 2008) the rate of loading is related to the liquid limit. Throughout the world local loading experience is used to choose a loading rate. The NGI recommendations (Sandbaekken et al., 1986) of loading at 0.5% to 1% strain per hour ($\Delta u_b / \Delta q$ in the range 2% to 7%) are often adopted.

Calculation of settlement from oedometer test data

Settlement (Δ) can be calculated from oedometer tests data by splitting the calculation into three parts, i.e. that involving loading up to p_c' , that beyond p_c' and creep (24):

$$\frac{\Delta}{H} = \frac{C_r}{1+e_0} \left[\log \frac{\sigma'_{v0} + \Delta \sigma'_{v1}}{\sigma'_{v0}} \right] + \frac{C_c}{1+e_0} \left[\log \frac{p_c' + \Delta \sigma'_{v2}}{p_c'} \right] + C_{sec} \Delta \log t$$

where:

H = layer thickness

C_c and C_r are the compression and recompression index (Figure 65)

σ_{v0}' = in situ effective stress

$\Delta\sigma_{v1}'$ = increases in stress between σ_{v0}' and p_c'

$\Delta\sigma_{v2}'$ = increase in stress between p_c' and the final applied stress

t = time

As an alternative (Scandinavian approach) the strain due to loading up to p_c' can be determined using the constrained modulus M at σ_{v0}' , i.e. M_0 :

$$\varepsilon = M_0 (p_c' - \sigma_{v0}') \quad (25)$$

In particular it needs to be stressed that this method of calculation though practical involves many simplifying assumptions especially for creep. Modern methods for determining creep, using for example the “isotache” methods (e.g. PLAXIS soft soil creep model) show much promise. However these require sophisticated soil input parameters and their output is particularly sensitive to parameters such as p_c' and OCR. Results may be more reliable for normally consolidated soils compared to those which have some degree of overconsolidation. Some research into use of these techniques for Irish soft soils is well warranted.

Typical 1D compression parameters

$C_c/1+e_0$

McCabe et al. (2014) studied the relationship between C_c and $C_c/1+e_0$ and a range of basic index properties for Irish soft clays, silts and marl. They found the best relationship was between $C_c/1+e_0$ and natural water content (w_n) as shown on Figure 67. This reasonably good fit is consistent with the finding earlier that field primary compression settlements are generally well-predicted, see Figure 9.

Figure 67. Relationship between $C_c/1+e_0$ and w_n from McCabe et al. (2014)

$C_r/1+e_0$

There is little data in the literature on values of C_r or $C_r/1+e_0$. The volume changes accompanying reloading or swelling are generally far lower than those accompanying consolidation. C_r is dependent on various factors including OCR and plasticity index (I_p), see Figure 68. The plot on Figure 68 is from Hight et al. (1987) with data from Mesri et al. (1978).

Figure 68. C_r against OCR as a function of I_p (from Hight et al., 1987)

Since C_c also increases with increasing I_p it could be expected that the ratio C_r/C_c falls in a narrow band. Hight et al. (1987) suggest that the average value of C_r/C_c is about 0.2 but stress that this ratio can vary especially due to OCR.

C_a/C_{sec} – international experience

The reader is again referred to Formulae 23 and 24 above for the definition of these two parameters which are linked by the factor $1+e_0$. Perhaps the best known relationship for C_a comes from the work of Mesri and Godlewski (1977) who found that C_a and C_c are closely related and that the ratio between C_a/C_c varied between 0.02 and 0.1 for a wide range of natural soils including peat, organic silt, highly sensitive clays as well as granular materials. Mesri and Choi (1985) suggested that:

- for inorganic soft clays $C_a/C_c = 0.04 \pm 0.01$
- for highly organic plastic soils $C_a/C_c = 0.05 \pm 0.01$

Some engineers prefer to use C_{sec} as it relates to strain rather than void ratio. The charts produced by Simons (1974) are a useful reference, see Figure 69.

Though not explicitly stated by the authors it is assumed that the C_{sec} values quoted above refer to normally consolidated conditions. As has been pointed out above (Figure 65) C_{sec} is stress dependent. An example of the relationship between C_{sec} and stress for the Änggården site in Sweden (Claesson, 2003) is presented on Figure 70. Here the C_{sec} values are plotted against the ratio of stress to the preconsolidation stress. At stresses below p_c' creep is very low and then increases significantly at or about p_c' and afterwards remains fairly uniform.

C_a/C_{sec} – Irish experience

The data summarised on Figure 9 confirms that creep is significant issue in Irish soft ground projects with reports of creep being underpredicted in six cases. There seems to be a particular issue with organic soils and especially calc marl. Long term creep at the Athlone Bypass was measured to be 5 mm to 10 mm / year. About 7 mm of creep was measured in the first 220 days after constructing the Bundoran / Ballyshannon Bypass. On the other hand very low creep rates were measured on the Skibbereen Bypass where the stresses applied were much less than the preconsolidation stress.

Figure 69. C_{sec} values from Simons (1974)

Figure 70. C_{sec} against normalised stress (Claesson, 2003)

Figure 71. C_{sec} from field and lab for (a) Arklow Bypass and (b) Limerick Tunnel

Very little laboratory data has been published on C_{sec} or C_a values for Irish soils. Farrell (1997) summarised data for the Bunratty Bypass site and found $C_{sec} \approx 0.00018w_n$ consistent with the data on Figure 69. Buggy and Peters (2007) found that the same relationship worked well for the Limerick Tunnel project. Typical values of $C_{sec} = 0.016$ were suggested in the literature for both the Athlone Bypass and the Galway Eastern Approach Road.

It is interesting to compare laboratory measured C_{sec} values with those derived from measured settlement data. Some examples for the Limerick Tunnel Project and for the Arklow Bypass are shown on Figure 71. In both cases the data refer to normally consolidated conditions. The field data needs to be treated with caution as it is not easy to reliably determine creep rates from a limited amount of field data. In general the lab data fits well with the field measurements. The field creep rates are arguably slightly higher. This seems to be particularly the case for Arklow. However the ground conditions at this site are highly complex (Figure 72) comprising about 7 m of highly organic clay / silt. Note in situ vane tests again seem to indicate very low strengths. The underprediction of the creep rates by the lab testing could be due to a combination of factors including:

- sample disturbance effects (U100 samples obtained),
- sample size effects (macro effects underestimated),
- rate effects (much faster in lab than in field).

This is an area which warrants more research work.

Using surcharging to reduce creep

Surcharge loading is often used to reduce long term creep effects. The principle of surcharge loading is that the soil is temporarily loaded to an effective stress (σ'_{vs}) which is higher than the final effective stress (σ'_{vt}) which it will experience under the permanent embankment load. This means that the soil will become 'artificially' over consolidated (OC) when under the final embankment load, thus reducing creep.

Figure 72. Arklow Bypass - Avoca Valley Crossing - ground conditions and soil properties

Figure 73. Effects of surcharging on creep (Ladd, 1971)

This is illustrated in Figure 73 (Ladd, 1971). The soil is loaded to stress level σ'_{vs} and allowed to consolidate. The value of C_{sec}/C_α is calculated as the slope of the curve between times t_p and t_R . The load is then removed and the soil is now at stress level σ'_{vf} . Swelling occurs following unloading until creep reappears at some time t_s , a new lower creep rate C'_{sec}/C'_α is now observed and can be calculated from the linear portion of the graph after t_s . The magnitude of this reduction depends on the amount of surcharge loading used.

Ladd (1971) defined the term AAOS (adjusted amount of surcharge) in order to help quantify how much surcharge is needed for a particular application. Based on his practical experience he developed some design line in order to facilitate practical application of his ideas (Figure 74).

$$AAOS = \frac{\sigma'_{vs} - \sigma'_{vf}}{\sigma'_{vf}} \quad (26)$$

Conroy et al. (2010) carried out some long term oedometer tests on samples of soft soil from the Limerick Tunnel project in order to test out Ladd's ideas on Irish soils.

The results obtained are shown on Figure 74 and it can be seen that trends observed provide good evidence that Ladd's method is applicable to the soft Limerick alluvial soils. Conroy et al. (2010) also summarised more recent published data from projects carried out since the original Ladd formulation and found these data also fitted well. They also emphasised that their findings relate primarily to inorganic silts and clays or soils with relatively low organic content (5%) such as the Shannon Estuary site in Ireland. Research is currently ongoing at UCD to test out these ideas on peat.

Buggy (2012) reports on pavement settlement for the Limerick Tunnel approach roads for a period of some 20 months after the roads were opened in the summer of 2010. The creep rates are very small as would be expected for the surcharged material.

Figure 74. Effect of surcharging on Limerick alluvium (Conroy et al., 2010)

c_v

The coefficient of consolidation (c_v), perhaps along with the coefficient of earth pressure at rest K_0 , is one of the most complicated parameters in soils mechanics. [Note limited data on K_0 for Irish soft soils can be found in Powell (2008)]. Unfortunately it plays a very significant role in the design of structures on soft soils. Some of the reasons for the complexity of the parameter are as follows:

- it is actually a composite parameter made up of a combination of k , m_v (or M) and γ_w (Equation 22),
- it is highly stress dependent especially around p_c' (Figure 65),
- various methods are available to obtain c_v (e.g. the Taylor root time and the Casagrande log time methods) but the values obtained for the same test using the different methods can vary widely, see for example Sridharan et al. (1991) or Cortellazzo (2002),
- installation of vertical drains can cause smearing and thus reduce the operational c_v (Figure 9)

Perhaps a way forward for determining c_v from laboratory tests is to obtain values of the component parts and combine them to derive c_v . Care needs to be taken to obtain the parameters for the same stress range as the practical problem under study.

It is also possible to obtain the coefficient of consolidation from a dissipation test in a CPTU (Lunne et al., 1997b). As pointed out by Randolph (2016) it is common practice to call the resulting parameter c_h but the subscript “h” should not be associated with purely horizontal drainage. Frequently the value of c_h from a dissipation test is found to be much larger than the parallel c_v value from a laboratory oedometer test, perhaps by an order of 2 to 10 (Mahmoodzadeh et al., 2014). Randolph (2016) showed by numerical modeling that even for isotropic soil conditions c_h from a dissipation test is some 3 to 5 times the equivalent c_v . According to these authors the reasons for the differences between the two sets of results are due partly to anisotropy but also due to the effects of rigidity index on the initial pore water pressures in the dissipation test as well as the more complicated stress path taken by the soil in the CPTU compared to the oedometer test. Macro / scale effects must also play a role. Various authors have compared c_v and c_h to back-analysed data from full-scale embankments. For example Balasubramaniam et al. (2010) found that the actual in situ rate of consolidation lay somewhere between c_v and c_h for embankments on Bangkok soft soils.

This is an area which well warrants more research, especially for Irish soft soil.

1D Compression parameters from V_s measurements

Similar to that described above for s_u it is possible to relate values of M_0 and p_c' (obtained using the Casagrande technique) to V_s .

Figure 75. M_0 and p_c' against V_s for Norwegian marine clays (L'Heureux and Long, 2017)

Figure 76. (a) M_0 and (b) p_c' against V_s for Irish soft clays

The logic behind this approach is again that the consolidation parameters and V_s are controlled by the same set of governing parameters e.g. effective stress. Such a relationship for Norwegian marine clay is shown on

Figure 75 (L'Heureux and Long, 2017). The fit is very encouraging and relatively high values of R^2 were obtained.

A similar set of plots for the Irish soft soils is presented in Figure 76. Again, like for s_u , only the best available samples are used. The finding for M_0 is similar to that for s_u in Irish soft soils with a clear trend being evident. There is some scatter in the data and the relationship falls below that of the Norwegian clays, showing once again that local correlations are necessary. The relationship between p_c' and V_s is very promising despite the difficulties in deriving p_c' for Irish soft soils.

Finally a plot of $C_c/1+e_0$ versus V_s is shown on Figure 77. Again there is some scatter in the data but the relationship is promising with a clear decrease in $C_c/1+e_0$ with increasing V_s . The correlation between V_s and $C_c/1+e_0$ is not as strong as that between w and $C_c/1+e_0$ (Figure 67).

Figure 77. $C_c/1+e_0$ against V_s for Irish soft soils

There seems to be very good promise in this approach especially given the difficulties in obtaining high quality samples of Irish soft soils. It is recommended that further V_s profiles are obtained on other interesting sites where good quality laboratory data is available, e.g. Loughmore Link, Clonmore Road etc. However it is clear that local correlations need to be made and reliance should not be placed on a correlations developed elsewhere.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Ireland has a complicated geology. As a result Irish soft soils can be complex both at macro and micro scale levels. A significant level of site investigation is necessary to characterise these soils properly.
2. A very good body of data is available from past experience of work on these soils. Approximately 40 well characterised sites have been identified. The development of these difficult sites represents a considerable achievement for Irish geotechnical engineers.
3. Although there is no doubt excavation and replacement has been the most common construction technique used, surcharging with vertical drains has dominated the techniques where details have been published.
4. The main lessons learned are that primary compression has been reasonably well predicted once the stress history is understood (i.e. p_c' important) but there can be difficulties in estimating rate of consolidation (c_v/c_h) and creep (C_{sec}). There have also been a number of well documented failures (s_u).
5. Shell and auger drilling is crude and unsafe and the technique often results in situations where piston sampling is done in material at least highly strained and maybe already failed, due to lack of stabilisation of the base of the borehole.
6. There is considerable Irish experience in understanding sample disturbance effects. Sampling in clay can destructurate the material leading to conservative design parameters. Sampling in silts and laminated soils can densify the material leading to non-conservative design parameters. It is recommended that only the best available samplers are used (new tubes / sharp cutting edge / fixed piston) and

- that fewer high quality samples are much more useful than many poor samples.
7. Given the issues with instability at the base of boreholes, the development of samplers such as the MOSTAP 70 is of great interest and should be trialled in Irish conditions.
 8. CPTU is a very powerful technique provided it is done properly and the Euro standard is followed.
 9. For clayey or silty clay soils the classical Robertson et al. (1986) charts work well in Irish conditions. The focus should be on q_t and B_q chart. The difficulties with obtaining reliable f_s values are of significant importance and therefore the q_t / R_f chart should be treated with caution. There seems to be a particular problem with characterising highly organic soils and especially peat. New developments such as the I_e index method and the Schneider et al. (2008), which focuses on u_2 data, show promising results in Irish conditions.
 10. Full flow probes (T-bar and piezoball) and SDMT (seismic dilatometer) have had limited use in Ireland but have given promising results.
 11. In the author's opinion shear wave velocity (V_s) measurements (together with CPTU) will be widely used world-wide in the future and the technique has much promise in Irish soft soils. It is useful for soil characterisation as well as giving estimates of soil properties such as M , p_c' and s_u . As only a limited database exists of such correlations in Irish soft soils, it is recommended that further field work is undertaken to obtain V_s profiles at sites where good laboratory data is available.
 12. Undrained shear strength (s_u) is a complex parameter but once used carefully lessons learned world-wide appear applicable to Irish soils. Good data can be obtained from laboratory CAUC, CAUE and DSS tests. Correlations between CPTU and full flow probe data and V_s measurements with s_u have been developed and appear promising.
 13. Laboratory UU tests in soft soils have no value and should be discontinued.
 14. Field vane s_u data needs to be treated with caution due to issues such as partial drainage during the tests, anisotropy and can insertion disturbance. New vane equipment seems very promising and should be trialled in Ireland.
 15. In oedometer testing shorter load increment holding time ($<$ conventional 24 hours) should be considered. Similarly CRS tests should be used more.
 16. Good correlations (with w or V_s) have been developed to allow estimation of C_c and p_c' .
 17. All 1D compression data (M , c_v , C_{sec}) should be analysed to a natural scale as well as the conventional $\log \sigma_v'$ approach.
 18. The coefficient of consolidation is a particularly complex and difficult parameter. It is a combination of several other parameters and is highly stress dependant. More work to understand c_v , particularly with the use of CPTU or piezoball dissipation tests, is well warranted.
 19. Field creep data has sometimes been greater than that expected from lab testing. This is also an area which warrants more effort, e.g. experimenting with modern analytical methods such as "isotache" approach (e.g. PLAXIS soft soil creep)
 20. The Ladd approach to surcharge design seems to work well in Irish soils.

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When I returned to UCD in 1996 I spent some time thinking about which direction our research should take. As UCD had a strong history in soil characterisation research, I spoke to David Hight of GCG / Imperial College who, in my opinion, is one of the world's leading authorities on this topic as can be seen in his 1998 Rankine Lecture. David was helpful and supportive. He said that if I wanted to learn about sampling of soft soil I should go and talk to Tom Lunne at the Norwegian Geotechnical Institute (NGI). Tom and I have become good friends and he has very patiently taught me many of the things I know about soft soils in the years since. I first went to the Norwegian University for Science and Technology (NTNU) in Trondheim for a sabbatical in 2001/2002 and have been fortunate enough to be able to spend time there every year since. There I encountered an excellent geotechnical group headed initially by another Rankine Lecturer Nilmar Janbu (25th Rankine Lecture in 1985). All of the staff there have been supportive to me. I should particularly mention the late Rolf Sandven who died suddenly in October 2016.

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Table A. Summary of well characterised soft ground sites in Ireland (Emb. Ht. – embankment height, E+R = excavate and replace, surch = surcharge, EPS = expanded polystyrene, BASP = bridge approach support piles, VCC = vibro concrete columns)

Soil type / Site No.	Site	Ground conditions	Emb. Ht. (m)	Soft Soil thk (m)	E+R	Surch	Vert drains	Geo-grid	EPS	Piles	Comments	Key references
Post glacial lake clays												
1	Athlone Bypass	Calc marl, over organic clay over laminated clay	8.5	15		✓	✓			Some BASP	c _{vh} a little lower than expected. Suspected smearing of vertical drains. Settlements over-predicted by 20%. Low long term creep of 5-10 mm/yr.	Morgan (1979), O'Riordan et al. (1982), Higgins (1984), Dauncey et al. (1987), Widdis (1988), Lyons (1992), O'Riordan (1997), Long and O'Riordan (2000), Long (2000), Long and O'Riordan (2001), Long (2002), Long (2003), Donohue et al. (2004), Long and Gudjonsson (2004), Long (2006b), Long (2006a), Colreavy et al. (2010), Long et al. (2014), Powell (2008), Colreavy (2017)
	Athlone Bypass Roscommon Road and Rail Bridge								✓			
2	Bogganfin, Athlone	Similar to Athlone										Donohue (2005), Donohue and Long (2010)
3	Galway Eastern Approach Road	Similar to Athlone Bypass	2	10		✓	✓				Large settlements. High creep rate, especially of calc marl	Flood and Eising (1986), Flood and Eising (1987), Rodgers (1989), Hunt (1991), Rodgers (1992), Rodgers and Joyce (1994), Rodgers (1997), Quigley et al. (2016)
4	Blackwater Bog, Co. Offaly	Similar to Athlone Bypass	6.5	10							No treatment. Settlements as predicted.	Fahy (1990), Rodgers and Fahy (1995)
5	Loughmore, Co. Limerick	Similar to Athlone Bypass	2	8		✓	✓				Rate of consolidation slower than expected. Suspected smearing of vertical drains. Significant failure occurred. Creep settlements as expected.	Gudjonsson (2003), Long and Gudjonsson (2004), Long et al. (2007b)

Soil type / Site No.	Site	Ground conditions	Emb. Ht. (m)	Soft Soil thk (m)	E+R	Surch	Vert drains	Geo-grid	EPS	Piles	Comments	Key references
6	Curlew Mountain Road	Similar to Athlone	2	12	✓							Loughrey (1997)
7	Portumna, Co. Galway	Similar to Athlone Bypass	3	7							No treatment. Settlements underpredicted due to lateral squeezing. High creep rates.	Conaty (2001), Conaty and Long (2002), Donohue et al. (2004), Long and Gudjonsson (2004), Donohue (2005), Long et al. (2007a)
8	Ballinasloe	Similar to Athlone Bypass										Donohue (2005), Donohue and Long (2008), Donohue and Long (2009), Donohue and Long (2010)
9	Cloondara, Co. Longford	Similar to Athlone							✓			Davitt and Killeen (1997), Rodgers (1997)
10	N15 Bundoran - Ballyshannon	Peat over calc marl over soft silt / clay	3.75	15.7	Peat to 3.7 m	✓	✓				Primary settlements well predicted. Creep 7 mm for first 220 days as predicted.	Long and Phoon (2004), Cooper and Martin (2006)
	N6 Kilbeggan to Athlone		2.1	14		✓	✓				Rate of consolidation more rapid than expected. Actual settlement somewhat smaller than anticipated.	Kelly (2008)
11	M17/N18 Gort to Tuam	Peat over calc marl over soft silt										Long et al. (2014)
12	Clonmore Link Road, Mullingar	Peat over calc marl over soft clay / silt	6	28						✓	Piles eventually used due to low strength, high compressibility and thickness of soft soils	This paper
Alluvial clays												
13	Mallow St. Bridge Approach Limerick City	Organic clayey silts	5.5	8		✓	✓				Drainage faster than expected. Settlements as expected.	Galbraith (1997)
14	Limerick Southern Ring Road – Phase 2	Organic clays	9.5	13	Shallow deposits	✓	✓	Some		BASP also used	Primary settlements as expected except one area where there was some overconsolidation. c_v high at low σ'_v . Small local failures.	Buggy and Peters (2007), Conroy et al. (2010), Bihs et al. (2010), Buggy and Curran (2011), Buggy and Curran (2012), Buggy (2012), Buggy (2013), Smith et al. (2013)

Soil type / Site No.	Site	Ground conditions	Emb. Ht. (m)	Soft Soil thk (m)	E+R	Surch	Vert drains	Geo-grid	EPS	Piles	Comments	Key references
15	Limerick Main Drainage Bunlicky / Corcanree	Organic clays	5.5	8		✓	✓				Recorded settlements slightly less than predicted. Rapid settlements. c_{vh} dependant on σ'_v .	Farrell (2000), Farrell and O'Donnell (2007), Buggy and Curran (2012)
16	Bunratty Bypass	Organic clays	11	12	Some	✓	✓	✓	Some little use of pfa		Settlements as expected. Reinforcement effective. One untreated section showed significant settlement. Importance of identifying p_c . c_{vh} dependant on σ'_v . Small local failures.	Fraser (1987), Mc Geever (1987), Mc Geever and Farrell (1988), Al-Ibrahim (1990), Connolly et al. (1990), Farrell et al. (1990), Farrell et al. (1997), Morris and Farrell (1997), Farrell (1997), Morris (1998), (Farrell, 2000), Farrell and O'Donnell (2007), Long et al. (2014)
17	Ardnacrusha, Co. Clare Shannon Hydro Scheme	Alluvial clays	Up to 18	Up to 10							No treatment (1920's). Some significant failures.	Harty (1953), Massarsch and Fives (1984), Massarsch et al. (1987), Lydon (1999), Lydon and Long (2001), Casey et al. (2002), Long et al. (2002),
18	Arklow Bypass North of River Avoca	Mixed sands, silts, peat and clays	9	5		✓	✓			Some BASP	Settlements slightly underpredicted. Creep rates higher than expected from lab tests	Long (1997), Higgins et al. (1999), Long and Callanan (1999), Long and Callanan (2000)
	Arklow Bypass South of River Avoca		9	5	✓						Performed well	
19	Cork City	Estuarine clays, silts and peats										Rodgers (1989), Rodgers and Joyce (1994), Rodgers (1997), Hemmingway and Long (2011), Long et al. (2015)
	Cork Ring Road (Tramore River) (19)		?	10	Partly to 6.5 m							Rodgers (1997)
20	Dunleer - Dundalk	Alluvial clays	4.7	5		✓	✓				$C_c/1+e_0$ from field and lab agree well. Some evidence of effect of p_c . Consolidation slightly faster than expected.	Magee and Farrell (1998), Farrell (2000)
21	Carrickmacross Bypass (N2)	Peat, calc marl and alluvial clays	1.5	8.7	Two areas up to 7 m	✓	None				Settlement occurred faster than predicted. Magnitude predicted reasonably well.	O'Donnell and Pentony (2006), Farrell and O'Donnell (2007)

Soil type / Site No.	Site	Ground conditions	Emb. Ht. (m)	Soft Soil thk (m)	E+R	Surch	Vert drains	Geo-grid	EPS	Piles	Comments	Key references
22	Wexford Main Drainage	Alluvial clays										Farrell and Fitzgerald (2001)
23	Car Park, Waterford	Alluvial clays	3	14.5		✓	✓					Farrell (2000), Farrell and O'Donnell (2007)
24	Waterford Bypass (N25) (Dooneen Marsh)	Alluvial clays	10	14		✓	✓				Measured performance agreed well with predictions. Creep perhaps greater than expected.	Phillips et al. (2012)
25	Carrick on Shannon	Peat over alluvial clays	2.5	4	✓	✓	None				Excavate / replace used after surcharging failed due to lack of drains and load which exceeded p_c' .	Long and Boylan (2013)
26	A2 Maydown to City of Derry Airport	Alluvial clays	Up to 4.4	14	Some	✓	✓				Settlements as predicted. c_v overestimated. Some creep	Raven and Anketell Jones (2012)
	Aclint / Keenagh, Co. Louth (N2)			18					✓			Dooley et al. (1995), Davitt and Killeen (1997)
	N2 Castleblaney			14	✓							Rodgers (1997)
	Silt											
27	Dunkettle, Co. Cork	Estuarine silts	7	12		✓	None				Settlements + rate of consolidation as expected. Horizontal drainage important. c_v somewhat dependant on σ_v' . Small local failures.	Flynn and Creed (1992), Creed (1997), Long and Ruiz (2001b), Long (2001), Long (2002), Stapleton (2003), Ruiz (2004), Long (2007)
28	Little Island, Co. Cork (East)	Estuarine silts	6	7.5		✓	None					Long (2002), Stapleton (2003)
	Little Island Vert drains section		6	7.5		✓	✓				Settlements agree reasonably well with predictions	
29	Kinsale, Co. Cork	Estuarine silts	4	6.8		✓	None				Settlements as expected. Rate of consolidation a little faster than expected.	Creed and Courtney (1997), Creed (1999), Stapleton (2003)

Soil type / Site No.	Site	Ground conditions	Emb. Ht. (m)	Soft Soil thk (m)	E+R	Surch	Vert drains	Geo-grid	EPS	Piles	Comments	Key references
Piled embankments												
	N25 Waterford Bypass Newrath Link (24)		10	13							Performed well	
	East of Shannon town		1.85	5						With VCC's	Performed well	Quigley et al. (2003)
	Drumsna to Jamestown Bypass (N2)		1.8								Some issues with position and verticality of piles but performed well	Orsmond (2012)
	Scramoge, Co. Roscommon		3.5								Initial settlement issues but since performed well	Orsmond (2012)
	Corravokeen, Co. Mayo										Timber piles. Performed well	Ryan et al. (2004), Orsmond (2012)
	Glen of the Downs, Co. Wicklow		8								Some issues with pile installation but performed well	Orsmond (2012)
	A1-N1 Flurry Bog, Co. Louth		3.5								Some issues with pile installation but performed well	Orsmond (2008), Orsmond (2009), Zhuang (2009), Orsmond (2012)
	N7 Annaholty and Drominboy Bogs, Co. Tipperary		6							Load transfer platform	Issue with piling. Designed as basal reinforced systems but built as piled slab	Orsmond (2012)

Table B. Summary of sampling comparative exercises carried out on Irish soils

Site	ELE 30°	ELE 10°	ELE 5° standard ¹	ELE 5° disp ² .	NGI95	MOSTAP 65	U100	Double U100	Block	Main references
Athlone Bypass	✓		✓			✓			✓ Sherbrooke	Long (2002), Long (2003), Long (2006a), Long (2006b)
Bogganfin	✓		✓	✓			✓			Donohue and Long (2010)
Loughmore	✓		✓							Long et al. (2007b)
Portumna	✓				✓					(Conaty and Long, 2002)
Ballinasloe			✓	✓			✓			Donohue and Long (2009), Donohue and Long (2010)
Dunkettle			✓		✓	✓				Long and Ruiz (2001b), Long (2001), Long (2002), Long (2007)
Sligo	✓				✓		✓	✓		Long and Ruiz (2001a), Long (2007)
Foynes Harbour Access Rd.		✓					✓			Carroll (2013)
Letterkenny		✓					✓		✓ Hand carved	Carroll and Long (2017)
Skibbereen		✓					✓			Carroll and Long (2017)

1: using conventional approach from the bottom of a cased shell and auger borehole

2: Scandinavian technique where sampler pushed through ground without borehole until sampling depth is reached